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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE CHECKLIST OF HOVERFLIES (DIPTERA: SYRPHIDAE) OF UKRAINE

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Prokhorov, A. V. Contributions to the Checklist of Hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) of Ukraine. — Despite a history of research dating back to 1864, the hoverfly fauna (Diptera: Syrphidae) of Ukraine has been studied unevenly across its diverse natural zones. This paper summarizes the results of intensive targeted sampling conducted between 2015 and 2024, focusing on previously understudied territories. Based on a dataset published via the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and material deposited in the I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology (SIZK), a checklist of 345 species is presented with detailed label data. Significantly, between 2016 and 2025, the author and his colleagues collected 67 species of hoverflies for the first time in Ukraine. This contribution fills major gaps in the distribution knowledge of syrphids across the Forest, Wood-and-Steppe, and Carpathian nature zones of the country. The materials presented herein precede the publication of the annotated catalogue of the hoverflies of Ukraine.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, faunistics, inventory.

Прохоров, О. В. Матеріали до списку мух-повисюхів (Diptera: Syrphidae) України. — Незважаючи на довгу історію досліджень, що сягає 1864 року, фауна повисюхових мух (Diptera: Syrphidae) України вивчена нерівномірно в межах її різноманітних природних зон. У цій статті підсумовано результати інтенсивних цілеспрямованих зборів, проведених у 2015–2024 роках, з особливою увагою до раніше малодосліджених територій. На основі набору даних, оприлюдненого через Глобальну інформаційну систему з біорізноманіття (GBIF), та матеріалів, що зберігаються в Інституті зоології ім. І. І. Шмальгаузена НАН України (SIZK), наведено список із 345 видів із детальними етикетковими даними. Важливо зазначити, що в період між 2016 та 2025 роками автор та його колеги вперше в Україні зібрали 67 видів повисюхових мух. Ця праця заповнює значні прогалини у знаннях про поширення сирфід у лісовій зоні, Лісостепу та Карпатах. Представлені тут матеріали передують публікації анованого каталогу повисюхових мух України.

Ключові слова: біорізноманіття, поширення, фауністика, інвентаризація.

Introduction

Ukraine occupies a strategic geographical position in Eastern Europe and is the second-largest country on the continent by area. Its diverse natural zones—Forest (Polissia), Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe, Broad-Leaved Forests, the Carpathian Mountains, and the Crimean Mountains—determine the richness of the country's fauna.

The study of hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) in Ukraine began more than 150 years ago (Nowicki, 1864), yet to date, the fauna has been studied very

unevenly. Targeted research has focused primarily on specific regions. The fauna of South-Eastern Ukraine, particularly the Kharkiv, Luhansk, and Donetsk regions, is well documented (Lezhenina, 1980, 1983, 1984, 1987, 1993, 2002; Skufyin & Bulli, 1987; Popov, 1994, 1997), as is that of the Crimean Peninsula (Bukovsky, 1936, 1940; Bukovsky & Stackelberg, 1932; Popov, 1998, 2001, 2003; Popov & Ussova, 2001; Popov et al., 2002). Separate studies have addressed the fauna of certain areas in the Carpathians (Shparyk, 2008; Shparyk & Sirenko, 2007; Sirenko & Shparyk, 2013) and Western Podolia

(Khmelnyskyi and Ternopil regions) (Lishchuk, 2009, 2012). Several papers have provided brief species lists from individual localities (Rogochaya, 1954; Tanskaya, 1992, 1993), while information on species distribution in the Polissia region was previously limited to a few historical works (Stackelberg, 1922, 1925, 1928, 1955, 1958, 1959; Kryshchal, 1949; Violovitsh, 1960; Stackelberg & Richter, 1968; Zaika et al., 2011).

Over the past decade, the author has actively collected material and observed the bionomy of hoverflies in the Polissia region; consequently, the fauna of the Kyiv, Zhytomyr, Rivne, and Chernihiv regions is now fairly well studied (Prokhorov & Popov, 2017; Prokhorov et al., 2017 a, b, 2018 d; Prokhorov, 2023). M. Zaika made a significant contribution to the study of the Kyiv and Sumy regions, conducting intensive sampling from early spring to late autumn for over a decade to expand the collection. Particular attention was also given to the Zakarpatska Region; despite prior special studies (Anikina, 1964, 1966, 1971, 1972), this region continues to yield new and interesting material, including finds previously unknown from the fauna of Ukraine (Prokhorov et al., 2018 a, b, c, 2020 a, b). Through years of regular fieldwork in Transcarpathia, our colleague V. Kavurka has contributed a significant number of rare species to the collection.

Between 2016 and 2025, the author of this article and his colleagues collected 67 species of hoverflies for the first time in Ukraine. Data on 46 of these species have already been published (Prokhorov & Popov, 2017; Prokhorov et al., 2017a, b; Prokhorov et al., 2018a, b, c, 2020a, b, 2023). This article presents a list of 345 species from Ukraine with label data, based primarily on published records from the GBIF database (Prokhorov, 2023) as well as on new, unpublished records by the author and his colleagues; excluding at least 15 species from his collection found in Ukraine for the first time, which are reserved for a forthcoming publication by the author.

Material and Methods

The material data presented for each species in the list are derived exclusively from a dataset compiled by the author, based on a collection assembled over ten years (2015–2024) dedicated to this group of dipterans. The vast majority of the material was collected by sweeping with an aerial entomological net, while some specimens were captured using a UV light trap. This paper relies on the dataset compiled by the author and published via the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) (Project ID: Cepa-LT-2017/10049).

All examined specimens were identified by the author and are deposited in the collection of the I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv (SIZK).

List of Material

Anasimya contracta Claussen & Torp, 1980

Material examined. Kyiv: Ivankovychi env., 50.2692 N, 30.4685 E, wet meadow (Vita River valley, 16.06.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Korneyev). **Zhytomyr:** Bronyky env., 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank, 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia, 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 04.06.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Anasimya interpuncta (Harris, 1776)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env., 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.5043 N, 30.28 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env., 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♀; 22.04.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env., 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17–18.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.2949 N, 26.2868 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Sarny env., 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia env., 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vyshevychi env., 50.6261 N, 29.4234 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 01.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Broad-Leaved Forests.

Anasimya lunulata (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Rivne: Hrabun env., 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog, 29.05.2021, 5 ♂, 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

Anasimya transfuga (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Khmelnytskyi: Solobkivtsi env., 49.0979 N, 26.8912 E, pond shore, 11.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

Baccha elongata (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env., 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env., 48.1576 N, 24.5283 E, glades in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env., 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2019, 1 ♀; 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 13.09.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env., 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env., 50.6835 N, 29.7106 E, mixed forest at the edge of the felling, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyyashivka env., 50.2798 N, 26.2711 E, edge of mixed forest and old overgrown felling, 14.06.2021, 1 ♀; Ilyyashivka env., 50.2826 N, 26.2837 E, mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Synevyr env., 48.526 N, 23.6642 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, near stream, 1048 m a.s.l., 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov);

Lypovets env., 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Blera fallax (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env., 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♂; 17.05.2017, 1 ♀; 11–13.05.2016, 1 ♀; 11–13.05.2019, 3 ♂, 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 27.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2020, 1 ♀; 15.05.2020, 1 ♂; 28.05.2020, 1 ♀; 12.05.2023, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♀; 23.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6536 N, 29.4932 E, edge of mixed forest and Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 03.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env., 50.6278 N, 29.4804 E, mixed forest, 16–18.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env., 50.29 N, 26.24 E, road in mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env., 48.4756 N, 23.7164 E, glade in *Picea* mountain forest (Pishkonja Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Synevyr env., 48.5223 N, 23.6836 E, swampy lake shore in *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Synevyr env., 48.5249 N, 23.6657 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env., 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env., 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Ivanivka env., 50.7019 N, 28.3641 E, felling in mixed forest, 10.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Brachyopa bicolor (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn, 51.0064 N, 31.8547 E, mixed forest, 11.05.2022, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Chernivtsi: Bernove env., 48.4893 N, 26.646 E, roadside (Dnister River valley), 22.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lenkivtsi env., 48.5145 N, 26.7932 E, edge of deciduous forest on the bottom of the ravine, 24.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kherson: Kherson, 46.6685 N, 32.644 E, 25.04.2020, 2 ♂, 3 ♀ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Dibrova env., 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 03.05.2008, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Zavorychi env., 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 06.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 01–02.05.2023, 5 ♂, 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env., 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.3012 N, 26.3029 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia, 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 14.04.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Steppe, Wood-and-Steppe.

Brachyopa dorsata Zetterstedt, 1837

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.501 N, 30.275 E, mixed forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Latorka env., 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Brachyopa insensilis Collin, 1939

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn, 51.0064 N, 31.8547 E, mixed forest, 11.05.2022, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Kyiv, 50.4596 N, 30.5402 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Trukhaniv Is. on Dnipro River), 29.04.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4728 N, 30.3209 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Brachyopa maculipennis Thompson, 1981

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn, 51.0064 N, 31.8547 E, mixed forest, 11.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Myhalky env., 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 01.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.3026 N, 26.2407 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Brachyopa panzeri Goffe, 1945

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6973 N, 22.4315 E, deciduous forest, 06.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.6911 N, 22.458 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Brachyopa pilosa Collin, 1939

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env., 51.037 N, 31.8001 E, edge of deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 4 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env., 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env., 50.69 N, 29.6966 E, mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5062 N, 30.2676 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♀ (G. Popov); Zavorychi env., 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 27.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2022, 1 ♂; 10.05.2022, 1 ♂; 25.04.2023, 3 ♂, 8 ♀; 01.05.2023, 1 ♂; 12.04.2024, 1 ♂; 28–29.04.2023, 10 ♂, 9 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♂; 29.04.2023, 6 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.04.2023, 1 ♀; 24.04.2023, 1 ♀; 12.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.654 N, 29.4878 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Brachyopa plena Collin, 1939

Material examined. Khmelnytskyi: Kavetchina, 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (G. Popov).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Brachypalpoides lentus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env., 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4708 N, 30.2915 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyashivka env., 50.2823 N, 26.2821 E, edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1

♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env., 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Pashkivtsi env., 48.81 N, 22.8676 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Pashkivtsi env., 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Brachypalpus chrysites Egger, 1859

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Yaremche env., 48.43 N, 24.43 E, Gorgany Mts., Elmy, 28.05.2007, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Brachypalpus laphriformis (Fallén, 1816)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn, 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♂; 27.04.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv, 50.5187 N, 30.5471 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env., 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.05.2020, 1 ♀; 22.05.2021, 1 ♀; 21–22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 04.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 15.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.05.2023, 1 ♂; 12.04.2024, 1 ♀; 08.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env., 50.3036 N, 26.299 E, deciduous forest, 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env., 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Brachypalpus valgus (Panzer, 1798)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn, 51.01 N, 31.8584 E, mixed forest, 15.04.2024, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env., 48.5341 N, 26.7643 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env., 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv, 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 09.04.2015, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 29.03.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv, 50.3357 N, 30.4896 E, city park (Theophania Park), 16.04.2018, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env., 50.69 N, 29.6966 E, mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6518 N, 29.5114 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 02.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env., 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.03.2019, 1 ♀; 10–13.04.2018, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 10.04.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.653 N, 29.4907 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and mixed forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5028 N, 30.2849 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 06.04.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀; 01.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6504 N, 29.5102 E, swampy glades in mixed forest,

07.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♂; 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env., 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia, 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 15.04.2022, 1 ♀; 27.03.2023, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia, 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 25.04.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Carpathians.

Caliprobola speciosa (Rossi, 1790)

Material examined. Kyiv: Muzychi, 50.352 N, 30.107 E, 15.05.2009, 1 ♂ (M. Nesterov); Kyiv, 50.5184 N, 30.5466 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv, 50.5396 N, 30.5452 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 26.05.2016, 1 ♂; Kyiv, 50.5197 N, 30.5452 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 28.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4728 N, 30.29 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6531 N, 29.4907 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 06.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env., 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.05.2017, 4 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Callicera aenea (Fabricius, 1777)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn, 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Kukshyn env., 51.2034 N, 31.6495 E, edge of deciduous forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env., 50.4724 N, 30.3144 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4708 N, 30.2938 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂; 11–13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5086 N, 30.2634 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂; Irpin env., 50.5012 N, 30.28 E, road in mixed forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env., 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env., 48.7902 N, 22.7843 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 17.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Lypovets env., 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Polissia, Carpathians.

Callicera aurata (Rossi, 1790)

Material examined. AR Krym: Roman-Kosh Mt. (Babugan-Yajla), 1300 m a.s.l., 01.08.1958, 1 ♀ (V. Ermolenko); Karabi-Yajla, upper edge of beech forest, 04.07.1961, 1 ♀ (V. Ermolenko). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env., 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env., 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 07.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Mereshor env., 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18–22.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: AR Krym, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Crimean Mountains, Carpathians.

***Callicera macquarti* Rondani, 1844**

Material examined. AR Krym: Chatyr-Dag, 24.05.1960, 1 ♀ (V. Ermolenko).

Distribution. Regions: AR Krym. **Zones:** Crimean Mountains.

***Ceriana conopsoides* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env., 51.0811 N, 31.8898 E, roadside, 04.06.2018, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Khmelnyskiy: Kavetchina, 48.5005 N, 26.6483 E, upper part of wooded ravine, roadside with thickets of flowering *Anthriscus sylvestris* (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kyiv, 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 21.05.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env., 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21.05.2016, 1 ♂; 20.05.2017, 1 ♀; 18.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2873 N, 30.556 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 06.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; 01.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6583 N, 29.5002 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 03.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.473 N, 30.2897 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 09.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 28.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha, 50.3039 N, 26.2498 E, roadside, near stream, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha, 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Ilyshyivka env., 50.2823 N, 26.2821 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env., 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog, 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Kocherhy env., 51.48 N, 33.8677 E, edge of deciduous forest, 28.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.05.2017, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Khmelnyskiy, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Carpathians.

***Chalcosyrphus (Xylotina) nemorum* (Fabricius, 1805)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env., 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♂; 05.06.2015, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 22.07.2015, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 07.08.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env., 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5029 N, 30.2799 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♀; Irpin env., 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; 24.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env., 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5023 N, 30.2824 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 29.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 10.04.2024, 1 ♀; 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mygalky env., 50.6535 N, 29.4859 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env., 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env., 50.3054 N,

26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env., 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Sarny env., 51.3204 N, 26.6714 E, strip of meadow vegetation near deciduous forest, 27.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 05.05.2017, 1 ♂; 07.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Carpathians.

***Chalcosyrphus (Xylotodes) eunotus* (Loew, 1873)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Potashnia env., 50.7141 N, 29.7288 E, Tal River floodplain forest (Tal River bank), 21.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.508 N, 30.2644 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6543 N, 29.4923 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀; 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

***Chalcosyrphus (Xylotodes) piger* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env., 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn, 51.0472 N, 31.8957 E, on the garden plot, 28.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Kodra env., 50.6278 N, 29.4804 E, mixed forest, 16.05.2015, 1 ♂; 30.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5156 N, 30.3005 E, mixed forest, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4708 N, 30.2908 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2016, 1 ♂; 11–13.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6556 N, 29.4998 E, old felling in mixed forest overgrown with *Prunus padus* near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6566 N, 29.5001 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and mixed forest, 27.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.65 N, 29.5 E, mixed forest, 25.08.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6475 N, 29.4866 E, mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4728 N, 30.3209 E, clearing in mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5023 N, 30.2824 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 20.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mygalky env., 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 07.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bilsk env., 51.4907 N, 27.284 E, mixed forest with flowering *Ledum palustre*, 28.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env., 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog, 29.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

***Chalcosyrphus (Xylotomima) femoratus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.5045 N, 30.2836 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Olshanytsia env., 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 05.06.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Broad-Leaved Forests.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotomima) pannonicus (Oldenberg, 1916)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Mereshor env., 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env., 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 23.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env., 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env., 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotomima) rufipes (Loew, 1873)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♂; 10.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env., 48.6911 N, 22.458 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env., 48.4169 N, 23.6793 E, beech forest, along stream, 22.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotomima) valgus (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env., 51.04 N, 31.7943 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn, 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.5045 N, 30.2836 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5008 N, 30.2747 E, Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂; Lisnyky env., 50.2961 N, 30.5348 E, edge of deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 06.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♂; 26.05.2023, 1 ♂; 04.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♂; 06.05.2024, 1 ♀; 04–06.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyyashivka env., 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2976 N, 26.2785 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 16.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Natalia env., 50.3747 N, 28.0445 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Broad-Leaved Forests.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) aerea Dufour, 1848

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env., 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn, 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 22.05.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Yabluneve env., 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 02.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Chernivtsi: Bernove, 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bernove, 48.4907 N, 26.6461 E, roadside (Dnister River valley), 22.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lenkivtsi env., 48.538 N, 26.7592 E, upper edge of deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env., 48.5483 N, 27.0314 E, edge of hornbeam-oak forest (bank of the Dnister River tributary), 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kherson: Antonivka env., 46.674 N, 32.7702 E, 15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). Kholmelytskyi: Kavetchina, 48.5005 N, 26.6483 E, upper part of wooded ravine, roadside with thickets of flowering *Anthriscus sylvestris* (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Myhalky env., 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 16.05.2015, 1 ♀; 21–22.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env., 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 23.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4708 N, 30.2915 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env., 50.4706 N, 30.2902 E, clearing in mixed

forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♂; 11.05.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5107 N, 30.2606 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂; 01.05.2018, 1 ♂; 01.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.04.2020, 1 ♂; 04.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env., 50.6334 N, 29.4817 E, road in mixed forest along the felling, 11.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6473 N, 29.4862 E, roadside, at the edge of mixed forest, 20.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mygalky env., 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs, 05.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Poltava: Poltava env., 23.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Rivne: Mosty, 50.3033 N, 26.1923 E, roadside, 13.05.2018, 1 ♂, 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Ilyyashivka, 50.2798 N, 26.2886 E, on the garden plot, 21.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Buderazh env., 50.3189 N, 26.15 E, meadow slopes, 23.05.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mosty, 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zbuzh env., 50.988 N, 26.3262 E, edge of mixed forest (Horyn River bank), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Ilyyashivka, 50.2819 N, 26.2821 E, roadside near mixed forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 08.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia env., 50.647 N, 29.4848 E, roadside (edge of mixed forest, 08.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Kholmelytskyi, Kyiv, Poltava, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Steppe, Wood-and-Steppe, Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) albipila Meigen, 1838

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env., 50.9689 N, 31.8613 E, edge of mixed forest, 31.03.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Dibrova env., 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 23.03.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka, 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 4 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv, 50.5051 N, 30.5465 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv, 50.465 N, 30.6741 E, Lisove Lake shore, 08.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv, 50.3515 N, 30.4815 E, wasteland (Theophania Park env.), 11.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env., 50.2973 N, 30.5443 E, glade in deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀; 27.04.2017, 1 ♂; 15.04.2018, 1 ♂; 10.04.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 22.04.2019, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5093 N, 30.2621 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 2 ♂, 2 ♀; 20.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env., 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 10.04.2018, 1 ♂; 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env., 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mygalky env., 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env., 48.6947 N, 22.4322 E, edge of the felling in deciduous forest, 06.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env., 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 14.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env., 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 30.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env., 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) albitarsis (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env., 48.5277 N, 26.7557 E, wet meadow, 22.05.2022, 1 ♀; Lenkivtsi env., 48.5341 N, 26.7643 E, wet meadow in the bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga Riv-

er valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env., 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Komariv env., 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 25.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Potashnia env., 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 4 ♂, 3 ♀; 24.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov, M. Zaika); Irpin env., 50.5089 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env., 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env., 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env., 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 6 ♂, 1 ♀; 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; 17–19.05.2019, 4 ♂, 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; 15.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Illyashivka env., 50.2798 N, 26.2711 E, edge of mixed forest and old overgrown felling, 14.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 12–15.05.2018, 3 ♂, 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env., 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env., 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Polianska Huta env., 48.7481 N, 22.7714 E, deciduous forest, 18.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env., 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env., 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Kamianytsia env., 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09–11.05.2017, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env., 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) barbata Loew, 1857

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env., 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Rivne:** Mosty, 50.3033 N, 26.1923 E, roadside, 13.05.2018, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Novomalyn, 50.2919 N, 26.3695 E, Zbytynka River bank, meadow, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Novomalyn env., 50.2995 N, 26.325 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Illyashivka, 50.2798 N, 26.2886 E, on the garden plot, 21.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mosty, 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3073 N, 26.2905 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 12.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Illyashivka, 50.2819 N, 26.2821 E, roadside near mixed forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2966 N, 26.2624 E, road in mixed forest near Zbytynka River floodplain, 13.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3019 N, 26.2871 E, edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 16.06.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20–22.05.2019, 8 ♂, 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ternopil:** Scala Podilska, 48.8373 N, 26.2185 E, Zbruch River valley, 26.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env., 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env., 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env., 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21–22.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env., 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23–24.07.2023, 1 ♂, 3 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env., 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Kamianytsia env., 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 06–08.05.2017, 2 ♂, 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Rivne, Ternopil, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) bergestammi Becker, 1894

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env., 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env., 50.2976 N, 26.2785 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Kholopychi env., 50.8088 N, 24.7492 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.07.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Sirnychky env., 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2020, 1 ♂, 2 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne, Volyn. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) brunnipennis Becker, 1894

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env., 50.5109 N, 30.2607 E, Irpin River floodplain near mixed forest, roadside, 11.04.2017, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & G. Popov); Irpin env., 50.5094 N, 30.2621 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env., 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 30.04.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia, 50.6404 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 27.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia, 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 08.04.2022, 1 ♀; 08.04.2024, 1 ♂; 24–25.04.2022, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia, 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 02.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia, 50.6408 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 12.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia, 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) canicularis (Panzer, 1801)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 28.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Vorokhta env. 48.1558 N, 24.5342 E, mountain meadow with flowering *Senecio* sp. at the upper edge of *Picea* forest, 09.08.2023, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1576 N, 24.5283 E, glades in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kvasy env. 48.1667 N, 24.4333 E, Petros Mt. env., 1480–1500 m a.s.l., 16.07.2011, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), thickets of *Petasites* sp.), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonka Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Kolochava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream, 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 5 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♀; 19.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8273 N, 23.1051 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Bilasovytzia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 07.09.2023, 1 ♂; 13.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Rodnykova Huta env. 48.7635 N, 22.8604 E, deciduous forest (Shypit River bank), 19.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) carbonaria Egger, 1860

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5341 N, 26.7643 E, wet meadow in the bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta

env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, mountain slope at the edge of *Picea* forest, roadside with flowering *Cirsium palustre*, 11–12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv (city park (Theophania Park), 03.06.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; 18.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2984 N, 26.2618 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 2 ♂; 4 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; 19.05.2019, 2 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀; 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Kamianytisia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 06–08.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) chloris (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Khmelnytskyi: Dovzhok env. 48.6799 N, 26.5016 E, edge of oak-hornbeam forest, 16.04.2007, 1 ♂ (A. Lishchuk). **Kyiv:** Kyiv (city park (Theophania Park), 11.04.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 03.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5572 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 15.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.27 N, 26.32 E, deciduous forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2977 N, 26.2635 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 18.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Bilasovytisia env. 48.8407 N, 23.0491 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 21.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 02.05.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 03.05.2023, 1 ♂; 06.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Bilasovytisia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 09–10.05.2023, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) cynocephala Loew, 1840

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.4997 N, 30.2859 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.4962 N, 30.3056 E, road in mixed forest, 05.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Sobolivka env. 50.7291 N, 30.8156 E, mixed forest near pond (Zalissia National Nature Park), 22.06.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Illyashivka env. 50.2833 N, 26.29 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esmar River valley, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 25.07.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) flavipes (Panzer, 1798)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Hvylyvka env. 50.9709 N, 31.8746 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Kyiv: Khodosivka 50.2643 N, 30.5321 E, meadow, 28.04.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.4596 N, 30.5402 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Trukhaniv Is. on Dnipro River), 29.04.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) fraterna (Meigen, 1830)

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; 18.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) gigantea (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Carpathians, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) grossa (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.9689 N, 31.8613 E, edge of mixed forest, 31.03.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 23.03.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4208 N, 30.4933 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), roadside, 29.03.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env. 50.6843 N, 29.6942 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.04.2017, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5039 N, 30.2798 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.03.2019, 1 ♂; 3 ♀; 08.04.2019, 1 ♀; 20.04.2019, 1 ♀; 10–13.04.2018, 2 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.471 N, 30.2865 E, old felling in mixed forest, 19.03.2020, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4956 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5028 N, 30.2849 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 06.04.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 10.04.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 09.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 17.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) himantopus (Panzer, 1798)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♂; 6 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.81 N, 22.8676 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) impressa Loew, 1840

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Spaska env. 48.3017 N, 25.7759 E, meadow, 430 m a.s.l., 24.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1541 N, 24.5308 E, *Picea* mountain

forest, roadside (between Pozhyshevska Mt. and Zarusliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1514 N, 24.5373 E, mountain meadow, southern slope (Pozhyshevska Mt.), 11.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, mountain slope at the edge of *Picea* forest, roadside with flowering *Cirsium palustre*, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 10.05.2016, 1 ♂; 31.05.2016, 1 ♂; 06.06.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 3 ♂; 4 ♀; 07.08.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Mosty 50.3033 N, 26.1923 E, roadside, 13.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 13.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Volyn:** Kholopychi env. 50.8088 N, 24.7492 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.07.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 03.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 05–08.05.2017, 4 ♂; 2 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Volyn, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) lasiopa Kowarz, 1885

Material examined. Kyiv: Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) latifrons (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env., 01.08.2004, 1 ♀ (M. Nestorov); Kyiv (city park), 15.05.2013, 1 ♂; Irpin env., 16.08.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka, 22.08.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Stare Selo env. 51.5952 N, 27.0902 E, meadows among thickets of woody vegetation), 21.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 12.08.2018, 1 ♂; 16.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Budyshcha env. 51.5 N, 33.98 E, 23.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) melanura melanura Becker, 1894

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Bilasovytsia env. 48.8407 N, 23.0491 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 21.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 30.04.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8258 N, 23.1018 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 10.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 02–03.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) mutabilis (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0091 N, 31.8611 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Ivankovychi env.

50.2681 N, 30.4339 E, wet meadow (Vita River valley, 29.06.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Korneyev); Kyiv 50.5215 N, 30.5526 E, Dnipro River floodplain meadow (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 09.06.2015, 1 ♂; Kyiv 50.523 N, 30.5535 E, Dnipro River floodplain meadow (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 26.05.2016, 1 ♀; Kyiv 50.5399 N, 30.546 E, Dnipro River floodplain meadow (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 31.05.2016, 1 ♀; Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 04.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2189 N, 30.5199 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 31.07.2017, 1 ♂; 04.07.2018, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E, 19–22.05.2018, 5 ♂; 9 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.3167 N, 30.5334 E, mixed forest, 12.06.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6999 N, 22.4319 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) nebulosa Verrall, 1871

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6999 N, 22.4319 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♀ (G. Popov); Latorka env. 48.851 N, 23.0768 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 22.04.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 30.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) orthotricha Vujić & Claussen, 1994

Material examined. AR Crimea: Simpheropol (Phontany (part of the city), 27.03.1983, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (S. Mosyakin). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: AR Crimea, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Crimean Mountains.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) pagana (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0052 N, 31.8619 E, mixed forest, 23.04.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Spaska env. 48.3017 N, 25.7759 E, meadow, 430 m a.s.l., 24.07.2019, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 10.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 08.08.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 08.04.2019, 1 ♂; 20.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 18.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 25.07.2018, 1 ♂; 21.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6999 N, 22.4319 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A.

Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8407 N, 23.0491 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 21.04.2023, 1 ♂; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8406 N, 23.0494 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 23.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 29.04.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8258 N, 23.1018 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 24.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.851 N, 23.0768 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 22–23.04.2023, 5 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bronyky env. 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank), 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) pascuorum Becker, 1894

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt), 02.05.2020, 1 ♀; Nizhyn env. 51.041 N, 31.8023 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 28.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2224 N, 30.5165 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields), 23.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂; 23–24.04.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6556 N, 29.4954 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6556 N, 29.4998 E, old felling in mixed forest overgrown with *Prunus padus* near Teteriv River floodplain, 01.05.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 02.05.2021, 1 ♂; 08.05.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6543 N, 29.4911 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.05.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.654 N, 29.4878 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 02.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) proxima (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Mylnyky env. 51.0314 N, 31.7752 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt), 13.05.2019, 1 ♂; 02.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Morivsk env. 51.11 N, 30.8869 E, oak planting along the cliff above the oxbow of the Desna River, 09.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Chernivtsi:** Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀; Lenkivtsi env. 48.5396 N, 26.7596 E, edge of deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River bank), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂; Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 25.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♂; 28.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 27.04.2017, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4706 N, 30.2902 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5207 N, 30.2713 E, Irpin River floodplain meadow, 23.08.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5062 N, 30.2676 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5055 N, 30.269 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂; 06.07.2018, 1 ♂; 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorochychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Zelenivka env. 46.3046 N, 29.9972 E, steppe slopes, 23.09.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3013 N,

26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.295 N, 26.282 E, edge of mixed forest near Zbytynka River floodplain, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; 16.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) psilophthalma Becker, 1894

Material examined. Kyiv: Khodosivka 50.2687 N, 30.5059 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5082 N, 30.2635 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) reniformis Hellén, 1930

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; 17–19.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 06.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 30.04.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) rhynchops Egger, 1860

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 10.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) rufimana Becker, 1894

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2626 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 29.04.2017, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4728 N, 30.3209 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–13.05.2019, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3015 N, 26.3022 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Bilasovytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 09.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) schnabli Becker, 1894

Material examined. Khmelnytskyi: Vykhvatnivtsi env. 48.6606 N, 26.8891 E, deciduous forest (Sovynyi Yar), 14.08.2006, 1 ♂ (A. Lishchuk). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 09.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi, Sumy. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) urbana (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 02.05.2020, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn 51.01 N, 31.8584 E, mixed forest, 15.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Donetsk: Nazarivka env. (Stone Tombs Reserve), 02.05.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Sergeev). Khmelnytskyi: Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4705 N, 30.2884 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 2 ♂; 4 ♀; 18.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 18.04.2019, 9 ♂; 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5042 N, 30.2704 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♀; 03.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 09.04.2020, 1 ♂; 3 ♀; 13.04.2020, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6557 N, 29.4998 E, mixed forest, 09.04.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6547 N, 29.4949 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 09.04.2020, 1 ♂; 13.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀; 28.04.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2021, 1 ♂; 10.05.2021, 1 ♀; 28.04.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytzia env. 48.8406 N, 23.0494 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 23.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 04–07.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 18.04.2021, 1 ♀; 20.04.2021, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 25.04.2022, 1 ♂; 04.04.2024, 1 ♂; 05–06.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Donetsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) uviformis Becker, 1894

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 1 ♂; 18.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 28–29.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) variabilis (Panzer, 1798)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2626 E, mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♀; 03.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.4962 N, 30.3056 E, road in mixed forest, 05.05.2016, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2626 E, mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀; Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.5348 E, edge of deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.05.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at

the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21–22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2871 E, edge of mixed forest and Zbytynka River floodplain, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Ilyyashivka env. 50.27 N, 26.32 E, deciduous forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀; Mosty env. 50.2889 N, 26.1886 E, deciduous forest (Zin?kiv kamin), 23.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Volyn: Simychyky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2020, 1 ♂; 13.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 03.05.2017, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.6973 N, 22.4316 E, deciduous forest, 07.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀; 07.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 08–10.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) velutina Loew, 1840

Material examined. Chernihiv: Khlopianky env. 51.7361 N, 32.7319 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 04.08.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6581 N, 29.4994 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 03.08.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6526 N, 29.4836 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs, 24.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (G. Popov). Rivne: Berezhnytsia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 27.07.2018, 1 ♀; 13.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) vernalis (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 02.05.2020, 5 ♂; 2 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Khlopianky env. 51.7361 N, 32.7319 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 04.08.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1558 N, 24.5342 E, mountain meadow with flowering *Senecio* sp. at the upper edge of *Picea* forest, 09.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 26.09.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 03.05.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 27.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; 08.04.2019, 1 ♂; 20.04.2019, 1 ♂; 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E), 19.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4956 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4949 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 13.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway,

30.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Mosty 50.3033 N, 26.1923 E, roadside, 13.05.2018, 1 ♀; Novomalyh 50.2919 N, 26.3695 E, Zbytynka River bank, meadow, 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; Mosty 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Berezhnytsia env. 51.4297 N, 26.4901 E, Horyn River valley, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂; Velyka Lyubasha 50.9549 N, 26.365 E, wet meadow (Zamchisko River valley), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; Sarny env. 51.3204 N, 26.6714 E, strip of meadow vegetation near deciduous forest, 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 10.05.2018, 1 ♂; 15.07.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 25.07.2018, 1 ♂; 13–16.08.2018, 3 ♂; 5 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8258 N, 23.1018 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.851 N, 23.0768 E, edge of mixed forest, along a stream, 22–24.04.2023, 8 ♂; 4 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Volyn, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) vulpina (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♂; Hvylyvka env. 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E, 21.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 04.07.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5224 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 25.07.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; Ilyashivka 50.2798 N, 26.2886 E, on the garden plot, 21.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Berezhnytsia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♂; 28.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 13.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6973 N, 22.4316 E, deciduous forest, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 02.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8273 N, 23.1051 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Convocheila) laticornis Rondani, 1857

Material examined. Chernihiv: Huta env. (mixed (pine) forest, 11.07.2001, 1 ♀ (P. Sheshurak). **Rivne:** Zbuzh env. 50.988 N, 26.3262 E, edge of mixed forest (Horyn River bank), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Eucartosyrphus) longula (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 12–13.08.2023, 2 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1602 N, 24.5217 E, raised bog at the

edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7081 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; Rudka env. 51.479 N, 25.688 E, mixed forest near swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Rivne. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Eucartosyrphus) ruffipes (Preyssl, 1793)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5506 N, 27.0285 E, upper edge of hornbeam-oak forest (Polyvaniv Yar), 25.05.2022, 1 ♂; Komariv env. 48.5513 N, 27.0283 E, hornbeam-oak forest (Polyvaniv Yar), 25.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 3 ♂; 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Khmelnyskyi:** Storonyche env. 50.2191 N, 26.584 E, dry meadow, 18.07.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 23.07.2015, 1 ♀; 10.08.2017, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; 07.08.2019, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2923 N, 30.5547 E, deciduous forest (dry stream bed), 07.08.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Zelenivka env. 46.3046 N, 29.9972 E, steppe slopes, 23.09.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Buderazh env. 50.3189 N, 26.15 E, meadow slopes, 23.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2966 N, 26.2624 E, road in mixed forest near Zbytynka River floodplain, 13.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.2871 E, edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 16.06.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 27.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytzia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 29.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Cheilosia (Eucartosyrphus) scutellata (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Morivsk env. 51.11 N, 30.8869 E, oak planting along the cliff above the oxbow of the Desna River, 09.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env. 48.5188 N, 26.7912 E, bottom of the ravine, along stream (Surscha River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhavska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 28.07.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.523 N, 30.5535 E, Dnipro River floodplain meadow (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 31.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 31.07.2017, 1 ♀; 03.09.2017, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 06.07.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 18.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6581 N, 29.4994 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀; Kotsiubynske env. 50.473 N, 30.2897 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6386 N, 29.4961 E, mixed forest, roadside, 17.07.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 18.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6487 N, 29.4885 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 02.09.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4865 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, edge of thickets of shrubs, 24.08.2023, 1 ♀; 02.09.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6537 N, 29.4863 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along channel), 02.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6973 N, 22.4316 E, deciduous forest, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1

♀; Latorka env. 48.8273 N, 23.1051 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.06.2018, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Selezivka env. 51.54 N, 28.1024 E, road in mixed forest, 15.07.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Floccocheila) illustrata (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♂; 18.05.2018, 1 ♀; Hvylyvka env. 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Chernivtsi:** Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1300–1400 m a.s.l., 31.07.2008, 1 ♀ (K. Martynova). **Khmelnitskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 16.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 20.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀; 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.297 N, 26.2789 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20–22.07.2023, 8 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Montanocheila) chrysocoma (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 02–03.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 29–30.04.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 05.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Cheilosia (Pollinocheila) fasciata Schiner & Egger, 1853

Material examined. Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 27.04.2017, 1 ♀; 10.04.2019, 3 ♂; 3 ♀; 22.04.2019, 1 ♀; 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2965 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 15.04.2018, 6 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) nigripes (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5277 N, 26.7557 E, wet meadow, 22.05.2022, 1 ♀; Lenkivtsi env. 48.5341 N, 26.7643 E, wet meadow in the bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 20.05.2021, 4 ♂; 6 ♀; 09.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Rivne: Remel env. 50.7328 N, 26.3834 E, meadow (Horyn River bank), 26.05.2021, 3 ♂; 7 ♀; Sarny env. 51.3204 N, 26.6714 E, strip of meadow vegetation near deciduous forest, 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 03.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) personata Loew, 1857

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.157 N, 24.529 E, mountain meadow (Zarosliak), 05.07.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1558 N, 24.5342 E, mountain meadow with flowering *Senecio* sp. at the upper edge of *Picea* forest, 09.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Trostianets env. 48.1688 N, 24.4165 E, sub-alpine meadow (Petros Mt.), 02.08.2005, 1 ♂ (I. Konovalova); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonka Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Kolochava env. 48.405 N, 23.7927 E, road in mixed forest (over the Prislop pass), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) pubera (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Material examined. Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & M. Zaika); 27.04.2017, 1 ♀; 10.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 29.04.2017, 1 ♀; 26.04.2018, 2 ♂; 2 ♀; 01.05.2018, 1 ♂; 20.04.2019, 1 ♂; 25.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Novomalyn 50.2919 N, 26.3695 E, Zbytynka River bank, meadow, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 18.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kotelnitsia env. 48.8195 N, 23.043 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) vicina (Zetterstedt, 1849)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.514 N, 26.7955 E, deciduous forest, along stream (Sursha River valley), 24.05.2022, 8 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25–26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 03.05.2017, 1 ♂; 05.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Chrysogaster cemiteriorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5095 N, 30.2618 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.07.2015, 1 ♂; 26.06.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5207 N, 30.2713 E, Irpin River floodplain meadow, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 2 ♂; 2 ♀; 30.06.2021, 4 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6526 N, 29.4836 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.07.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Berezhnysia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.2871 E, edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 16.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Chrysogaster solstitialis (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Khlopianyky env. 51.7277 N, 32.7245 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 01.08.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kodra env. 50.6368 N, 29.4748 E, mixed forest, 12.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5095 N, 30.2618 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6569 N, 29.5002 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and mixed forest, 06.07.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2732 E, mixed forest along railway, 19.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6581 N, 29.4994 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 03.08.2020, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Balyko-Shchuchynka env. 49.9624 N, 31.1191 E, ravine in deciduous forest, 05.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6536 N, 29.4932 E, edge of mixed forest and Teteriv River floodplain forest, 26.06.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 31.07.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 21.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 18.06.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6557 N, 29.4931 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 14.06.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 04.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 30.06.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3011 N, 26.3042 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 12.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3073 N, 26.2905 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 12.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7002 N, 22.4398 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7803 N, 22.7598 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 13.06.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7691 N, 22.7418 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 13.06.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Chrysotoxum arcuatum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Khreshchatyk 48.6314 N, 25.7377 E, meadow slope on the right bank of the Dnister River (near Zalishchyky), 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (R. Kryvosheyev). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 28.07.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Vorokhta env. 48.1558 N, 24.5342 E, mountain meadow with flowering *Senecio* sp. at the upper edge of *Picea* forest, 09.08.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.4756 N, 23.7164 E, glade in *Picea* mountain forest (Pishkonja Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Chrysotoxum bicinctum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Khlopianyky env. 51.7276 N, 32.7296 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.08.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.155 N, 24.5338 E, upper edge of *Picea* mountain forest, roadside, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Khmelnyskyi:** Storonyche env. 50.2191 N, 26.584 E, dry meadow, 18.07.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.221 N, 30.5179 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 05.07.2017, 1 ♀; 31.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2228 N, 30.5196 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 25.07.2021, 1 ♀; Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5224 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 03.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6987 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 27.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream, 10.06.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20–23.07.2023, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 15.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Chrysotoxum cautum (Harris, 1778)

Material examined. Cherkasy: Buchak Lake env. 49.8568 N, 31.4371 E, edge of deciduous forest, 10.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Chernihiv:** Mala Koshellivka env. 51.1338 N, 31.9491 E, edge of mixed forest, 26.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kherson:** Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E, 14.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5103 N, 30.2621 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21.05.2016, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5218 N, 30.5505 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 28.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂; 15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain

forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♀; 05.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4902 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 08.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.05.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Maryanivka env. 46.3995 N, 30.4996 E, forest shelter belt, 23.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Cherkasy, Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Odesa. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Chrysotoxum elegans Loew, 1841

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2189 N, 30.5199 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 05.07.2017, 1 ♂; 31.07.2017, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E), 22.05.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5224 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 25.07.2021, 1 ♀; 03.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 22.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, mountain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 23.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20–22.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Chrysotoxum fasciolatum (De Geer, 1776)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.157 N, 24.529 E, mountain meadow, 05.07.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Shparyk). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Chrysotoxum festivum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhynske env. 50.9852 N, 31.7919 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.06.2019, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0091 N, 31.8611 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Mala Koshellivka env. 51.1338 N, 31.9491 E, edge of mixed forest, 26.05.2024, 1 ♂; Khlopianky env. 51.7562 N, 32.6855 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.08.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhynske 51.005 N, 31.8209 E, Viunytisia River valley meadow, 08.09.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kherson:** Strohanivka env. 46.2386 N, 33.8132 E, steppe, 03.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5088 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6557 N, 29.4931 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 14.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21–22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mosty 50.3048 N, 26.1932 E, roadside, 13.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytnyanka River floodplain meadow at the edge

of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; Illyashivka env. 50.2787 N, 26.2818 E, edge of deciduous forest, 21.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hlynye env. 51.5633 N, 27.4292 E, Stvyha River bank), 20.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Kholopychi env. 50.8088 N, 24.7492 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.07.2019, 1 ♀; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.405 N, 23.7927 E, road in mixed forest (over the Prislup pass), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 29.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8498 N, 23.0475 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 11.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 06.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Chrysotoxum intermedium Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Kherson: Strohanivka env. 46.2386 N, 33.8132 E, steppe, 13.09.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov). **Odesa:** Lymanske 46.6859 N, 29.9767 E, Cuciurgan Reservoir bank, 23.05.1951, 1 ♀ (V. Ermolenko).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson, Odesa. **Zones:** Steppe.

Chrysotoxum lessonae Giglio-Tos, 1890

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 6 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♂; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 27.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Chrysotoxum octomaculatum Curtis, 1837

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 27.05.2018, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6492 N, 29.4891 E, edge of mixed forest and Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6323 N, 29.4829 E, felling in mixed forest, 14.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01–02.06.2022, 4 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6353 N, 29.4775 E, mixed forest, 16–17.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21–22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2834 N, 26.2899 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♂; Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11–16.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila

Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Chrysotoxum vernale Loew, 1841

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0496 N, 31.8726 E, pond shore, 05.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kherson: Antonivka env. 46.674 N, 32.7702 E, 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Kodra env. 50.6353 N, 29.4775 E, mixed forest, 30.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♀; 11.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♂; 27.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Illyashivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6999 N, 22.4319 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Zhytomyr: Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Ivanivka env. 50.7019 N, 28.3641 E, felling in mixed forest, 10.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Chrysotoxum verralli (Collin, 1940)

Material examined. Kyiv: Zavorychi env. 50.6862 N, 31.1083 E, roadside (edge of the meadow, 16.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.06.2017, 1 ♂; 26.06.2018, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5054 N, 30.2704 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂; 23.07.2020, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 27.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 28.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4868 E, aspen grove in floodplain meadow (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6571 N, 29.4991 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, near channel, 25–26.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Stare Selo env. 51.5952 N, 27.0902 E, meadows among thickets of woody vegetation, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytzia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Criorhina asilica (Fallén, 1816)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2931 N, 30.5519 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 20.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske

env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.49 E, edge of mixed forest and Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 20.05.2023, 1 ♂; 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14–15.05.2023, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Illyashivka 50.2789 N, 26.2819 E, edge of deciduous forest (with overmature trees of *Tilia* sp.), 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, road in mixed forest, 11–12.05.2018, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Volyn: Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 19.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Polianska Huta env. 48.7481 N, 22.7714 E, deciduous forest, 18.05.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 06–07.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.05.2017, 6 ♂; 6 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Criorhina floccosa (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6992 N, 22.4293 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Criorhina pachymera Egger, 1858

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14–15.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Criorhina ranunculi (Panzer, 1804)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.01 N, 31.8584 E, mixed forest, 15.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5051 N, 30.5465 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4713 N, 30.2993 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 13.04.2018, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5063 N, 30.5455 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), edge of floodplain forest, 17.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6518 N, 29.5114 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 06.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro

River, city park), 18.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5033 N, 30.2785 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.471 N, 30.2865 E, old felling in mixed forest, 19.03.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 22.04.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6555 N, 29.4953 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 29.04.2023, 1 ♀; 01.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 31.03.2024, 1 ♀; Kodra env. 50.6301 N, 29.4802 E, clearing in mixed forest, 02.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 17–18.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6835 N, 31.0901 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3015 N, 26.3022 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 14.04.2022, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 24.04.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 04.04.2024, 1 ♀; 07.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Dasysyrphus albostratus (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.037 N, 31.8001 E, edge of deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2781 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 29.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6539 N, 29.4861 E, dry meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–17.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3003 N, 26.2554 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Ilyshivka env. 50.2816 N, 26.2712 E, edge of deciduous forest and agricultural field), 14.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7989 N, 22.8001 E, mountain meadow (Polony-na-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 18.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 19–20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Dasysyrphus friuliensis (van der Goot, 1960)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.157 N, 24.529 E, mountain meadow, 05.07.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Shpyryk).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Dasysyrphus hilaris (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed

forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 21.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.654 N, 29.4878 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 06.05.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 14.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 12.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2973 N, 26.2786 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6523 N, 29.4756 E, Teteriv River floodplain, 11.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Dasysyrphus neovenustus Soszyński, Mielczarek & Tofilski, 2013

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 30.04.2010, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 21.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 5 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4978 N, 30.3018 E, road in mixed forest near Lyubka River), 17.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.4964 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4974 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 15.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 17.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♂; 22.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 12.04.2024, 4 ♂; 1 ♀; 14.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♀; 23–24.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 02.05.2021, 1 ♂; Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♂; Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 09.05.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 09.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 24.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Mosty 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 02.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Dasysyrphus pauxillus (Williston, 1887)

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 25.04.2010, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 19.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.04.2023, 1 ♂; 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 08.04.2024, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 04–05.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Dasysyrphus tricinctus (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Mylnyky env. 51.0314 N, 31.7752 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂; Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 31.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08–15.05.2020, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♀; Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytisia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6408 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 07.05.2021, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 26.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Dasysyrphus venustus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Mylnyky env. 51.0314 N, 31.7752 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂; Hvylyvka env. 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn env. 51.041 N, 31.8023 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 28.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 25.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 26.05.2022, 1 ♀

(V. Kavrka). Kyiv: Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 27.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5063 N, 30.2675 E, mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4728 N, 30.3209 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♂; 16.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 01.05.2023, 1 ♂; 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 14.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13–15.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6278 N, 29.4804 E, mixed forest, 16–17.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28–29.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Volyn: Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; 13.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). Zakarpatska: Kamianytisia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Kamianytisia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 05–08.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 09–10.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). Zhytomyr: Zelena Poliana env. 50.6001 N, 28.1255 E, mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♀; Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Didea alneti (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kodra env. 50.6318 N, 29.4851 E, mixed forest, 18.05.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 06.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 5 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4976 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyashivka env. 50.2822 N, 26.282 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Zakarpatska: Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6408 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 25.04.2020, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2020, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 16.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Didea fasciata Macquart, 1834

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3444 N, 30.4858 E, city park (Theophania Park), 10.05.2016, 1 ♀; 16.10.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 27.07.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4951 E, road in mixed forest, 03.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs, 24.08.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 06.09.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4843 E, grassy vegetation on the bank of the channel, 17.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, Esman River valley, 28.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 07.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 10.10.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Sumy, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Didea intermedia Loew, 1854

Material examined. Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 23.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2177 N, 30.5226 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 04.07.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4544 N, 30.3382 E, roadside, near Sviatoshinske Lake, 26.09.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6498 N, 29.5105 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4955 E, mixed forest, 03.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Staiky env. 50.0514 N, 30.9335 E, on the garden plot at the edge of mixed forest, 28.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21–22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4969 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, near channel, 25–26.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.294 N, 26.2876 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2020, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4724 E, on the garden plot, 11.10.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Doros profuges (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5088 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Epistrophe diaphana (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Khlopianyky 51.7444 N, 32.7164 E, meadow, 10.06.2011, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Kukshin env. 51.176 N, 31.632 E, edge of deciduous forest, 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 27.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Epistrophe eligans (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 11.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 26.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.509 N, 30.2625 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Maryanivka env. 46.3995 N, 30.4996 E, forest shelter belt, 24.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3021 N, 26.2843 E, edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2965 N, 26.2416 E, mixed forest among lowland calcareous fens, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂; Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11–13.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Simychnyky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2022, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 13.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Epistrophe flava Doczkal & Schmid, 1994

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Hvylyvka env. 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 05.06.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4713 N, 30.2993 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 09.06.2021,

1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–13.05.2019, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♀; Ilyyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11–13.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 09–11.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Epistrophe grossulariae (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Potashnia env. 50.7141 N, 29.7288 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Mizhhirya env. 50.733 N, 24.7825 E, ravine, 15.07.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Volyn, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Epistrophe melanostoma (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Nizhyn 51.01 N, 31.8584 E, mixed forest, 15.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♀; Kotsiubynske env. 50.5022 N, 30.3024 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 17.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; 18.04.2019, 4 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5082 N, 30.2636 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 10.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5063 N, 30.2675 E, mixed forest along railway, 25.04.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 09.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀; 14.04.2024, 1 ♂; 01.05.2024, 1 ♀; 03.05.2024, 1 ♀; 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Epistrophe nitidicollis (Megerle in Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Hvylyvka env. 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env. 48.538 N, 26.7592 E, upper edge of deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River flood-

plain, roadside (near mixed forest, 30.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 10.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.05.2016, 1 ♀; 17.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 21.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5064 N, 30.2673 E, mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 24.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 06.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 28.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀; 03.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 03.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 13–18.05.2020, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Maryanivka env. 46.3995 N, 30.4996 E, forest shelter belt), 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Zbuzh env. 50.988 N, 26.3262 E, Horyn River bank near mixed forest, 27.05.2021, 1 ♀; Ilyyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11–13.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 13.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream), 10.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 03–08.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♂; Ivanivka env. 50.7019 N, 28.3641 E, felling in mixed forest, 10.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Epistrophe ochrostoma (Zetterstedt, 1849)

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.44 N, 30.58 E, Venetsianskiy Is. on Dnipro River, floodplain forest, city park (Hidropark), 13.04.2007, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 1 ♂; 18.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Epistrophe olgae Mutin, 1990

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5063 N, 30.2675 E, mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5064 N, 30.2673 E, mixed forest along railway, 01.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 06.05.2022, 1 ♂; 10.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env.

50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 24.04.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♂; 01.05.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♂; 14.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20–25.04.2019, 6 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Epistropheuchroma (Kowarz, 1885)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.968 N, 31.8722 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 05.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5082 N, 30.2636 E, mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2143 N, 30.5268 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 23.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 29.04.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 10.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 17–18.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 23–24.04.2020, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyshivka env. 50.2824 N, 26.2821 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovtytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 09.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 07–08.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Episyrphus balteatus (De Geer, 1776)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.0818 N, 31.8899 E, dry meadow, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀; Morivsk 51.0883 N, 30.8823 E, on the garden plot, 10.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kherson:** Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E, 14.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). **Kyiv:** Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.06.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 23.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 30.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6476 N, 29.4868 E, road in mixed forest, 17.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural

fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 10.04.2018, 1 ♀; 31.03.2019, 1 ♀; 08.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5086 N, 30.2632 E, mixed forest, 29.06.2018, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev); Kotsiubynske env. 50.471 N, 30.2865 E, old felling in mixed forest, 19.03.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6505 N, 29.5105 E, dry swamp in mixed forest, 27.03.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4949 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.04.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; 01.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.655 N, 29.4955 E, old felling in mixed forest, 09.11.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 08–15.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 25–26.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Mykolaiv:** Ostrivka env. 46.7242 N, 31.7378 E, forest shelter belt, 22.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Zbuzh env. 50.9902 N, 26.3203 E, meadow (Horyn River valley), 14.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Berezhnitsia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5096 N, 33.9062 E, Esman River valley, 08.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Ternopil:** Hutysko env. 49.4039 N, 24.8315 E, meadow slopes, 16.07.2019, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev); Romanove Selo env. 49.546 N, 25.9346 E, road in deciduous forest, 11.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Volyn:** Simyichky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 13.05.2020, 1 ♀; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂; 07–08.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khochyne env. 51.5 N, 27.8818 E, Ubort River valley, 17.07.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 10.10.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherson, Kyiv, Mykolaiv, Rivne, Sumy, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eriozona syrphoides (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Stara Huta 48.63 N, 24.21 E, mixed forest (Gorgany Mts.), 22.06.2013, 1 ♀ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1622 N, 24.5361 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Zarosliak and Pozhyzhevsk Mt.), 09.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1541 N, 24.5308 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Pozhyzhevsk Mt. and Zarosliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; Vorokhta env. 48.144 N, 24.5494 E, raised bog in *Picea* mountain forest, 11.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Synevyr env. 48.526 N, 23.6642 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, near stream, 1048 m a.s.l., 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Eristalinus (Eristalinus) sepulchralis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kherson:** Antonivka env. 46.674 N, 32.7702 E, 15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). **Khmelnitskyi:** Solobkivtsi env. 49.0979 N, 26.8912 E, pond shore, 11.07.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 22.07.2015, 1 ♂; 10.08.2017, 1 ♂; 17.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4706 N, 30.2902 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6581 N, 29.4994 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 03.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kaharlyk 49.865 N, 30.8096 E, on the garden plot, 24.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4865 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, edge of thickets of shrubs, 24.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6539 N, 29.4861 E, dry meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Maiaky

env. 46.4123 N, 30.165 E, Dniester River floodplain, 24.09.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Rivne:** Ilyyashivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Vinnitsia:** Stryzhavka env. 49.2894 N, 28.474 E, edge of Southern Bug River floodplain forest, 20.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♂; Ukrainka env. 50.7607 N, 29.4129 E, Irsha River floodplain meadow, 17.08.2020, 1 ♀; Bronyky env. 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank, 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Sumy, Vinnitsia, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eristalinus (Lathyrphthalmus) aeneus (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0052 N, 31.8619 E, mixed forest, 29.04.2019, 1 ♀; Hvylyivka env. 50.9689 N, 31.8613 E, edge of mixed forest, 31.03.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0541 N, 31.9063 E, Oster River bank, 03.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 11.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 04.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 08.04.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 10.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Staiky env. 50.0514 N, 30.9335 E, on the garden plot at the edge of mixed forest, 28.09.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Karolino-Bugaz 46.1643 N, 30.5631 E, sandy seashore, 23.07.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Maryanivka env. 46.3995 N, 30.4996 E, forest shelter belt, 23.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Prymorske env. 45.6756 N, 29.8689 E, steppe area on the Black Sea coast, 07–08.06.2023, 1 ♀ (Ye. Khalaim). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianitsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 15.04.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 23.04.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 13.06.2023, 1 ♀; 26.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Odesa, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) alpina (Panzer, 1798)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianitsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) arbustorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 05.06.2018, 1 ♀; Nizhynske env. 50.9882 N, 31.8012 E, wet meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 01.06.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0541 N, 31.9063 E, Oster River bank, 03.06.2024, 1 ♀; Khlopianky env. 51.7361 N, 32.7319 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 04.08.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Chernivtsi:** Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dniester River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂; Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dniester River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kherson:** Antonivka env. 46.674 N, 32.7702 E, 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). **Khmelnytskyi:** Dubivka env. 49.1327 N, 26.4427 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.08.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5095 N, 30.2629 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5219 N, 30.5536 E, Dniipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dniipro River), 09.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5088 N, 30.2631

E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2177 N, 30.5226 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 05.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 13.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5093 N, 30.2622 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kaharlyk 49.865 N, 30.8096 E, on the garden plot, 24.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Lisnyky env. 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 09.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5224 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 03.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 06.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Ulianyky env. 49.9141 N, 31.1229 E, meadow along stream on the bottom of the ravine, 27.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Libental env. 46.4406 N, 30.5164 E, forest shelter belt, 22.07.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Berezhyno env. 46.1917 N, 29.2613 E, steppe ravine, 14.08.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Maryanivka env. 46.3995 N, 30.4996 E, forest shelter belt, 23–24.04.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Rivne:** Berezhnitsia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianitsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianitsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianitsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 22.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 19.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Ukrainka env. 50.7607 N, 29.4129 E, Irsha River floodplain meadow, 17.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4724 E, on the garden plot, 25.08.2021, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 25.04.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) cryptarum (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Rivne: Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) horticola (De Geer, 1776)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4713 N, 30.2993 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♀; 11.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02–04.06.2016, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2977 N, 26.2399 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀; Bilsk env. 51.4725 N, 27.2646 E, road in swamped mixed forest (between Bilsk and Khmil), 20.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.6748 N, 27.114 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy

slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) intricaria (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 05.06.2018, 1 ♂; Nizhynske env. 50.9882 N, 31.8012 E, wet meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 01.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4705 N, 30.2872 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♂; 17.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.293 N, 30.5519 E, deciduous forest, 24.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2198 N, 30.5189 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (lower part of meadow slopes), 04.07.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 07.08.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6586 N, 29.5 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rzhyschiv 49.9664 N, 31.1046 E, steppe ravine), 06.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5044 N, 30.2737 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 29.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 15.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 06.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 15.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 09.07.2024, 1 ♂; Kodra env. 50.6374 N, 29.4735 E, road in mixed forest, 29.07.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6537 N, 29.4863 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 07.08.2024, 1 ♂; 19.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03–05.06.2015, 4 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 22–23.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2977 N, 26.2399 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.4789 N, 25.6854 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytisia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Selezivka env. 51.54 N, 28.1024 E, road in mixed forest, 15.07.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) jugorum Egger, 1858

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 2 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytisia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytisia env. 48.8498 N, 23.0475 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 11.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 19–20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) nemorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6556 N, 29.4998 E, old felling in mixed forest overgrown with *Prunus padus* near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 24.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5094 N, 30.262 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 29.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♂; 24.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 15.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytisia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 22.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytisia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 08–09.06.2018, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) obscura Loew, 1866

Material examined. Chernihiv: Khlopianyky env. 51.7277 N, 32.7245 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 01.08.2024, 1 ♂; Khlopianyky env. 51.7562 N, 32.6855 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.08.2024, 2 ♂; 2 ♀; Khlopianyky env. 51.7361 N, 32.7319 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 04.08.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Khmelnitskyi:** Storonyche env. 50.2191 N, 26.584 E, dry meadow, 18.07.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♂; 3 ♀; 02.06.2016, 2 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4713 N, 30.2993 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.473 N, 30.2897 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 29.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4902 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 08.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 15.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6304 N, 29.4865 E, road in mixed forest, 14.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6526 N, 29.4836 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 09.07.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.294 N, 26.2876 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed

forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2938 N, 26.2891 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.6748 N, 27.114 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 2 ♂; 3 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 16.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Kholopychi env. 50.8088 N, 24.7492 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.07.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) oestracea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Divychyky env. 50.0441 N, 31.273 E, sandy arena of the Dnipro River left bank), 20.06.2021, 1 ♀ (O. Galkin); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (glades), 10.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 16.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) pertinax (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.522 N, 30.2763 E, Irpin River floodplain meadow, 05.07.2015, 1 ♂; Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 13.04.2018, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 07.08.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5044 N, 30.2737 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 29.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5021 N, 30.2828 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 08.09.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♀; 24.08.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4875 E, thickets of shrubs along channel at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.10.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 22–23.07.2015, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2984 N, 26.2602 E, edge of Zbytnyka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bilsk env. 51.4907 N, 27.284 E, mixed forest with flowering *Ledum palustre*, 28.05.2021, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:**

Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 13.05.2020, 1 ♀; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Mereshor env. 48.4134 N, 23.6667 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8258 N, 23.1018 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8273 N, 23.1051 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 19.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 02–03.05.2023, 3 ♂; 2 ♀; Latorka env. 48.851 N, 23.0768 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 22–23.04.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Ukrainka env. 50.7607 N, 29.4129 E, Irsha River floodplain meadow, 17.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Zelena Poliana env. 50.6001 N, 28.1255 E, mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) picea (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6833 N, 29.7101 E, felling in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 5 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6556 N, 29.4998 E, old felling in mixed forest overgrown with *Prunus padus* near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 24.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 24.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.04.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2969 N, 26.2389 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 15.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♀; 06.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Eristalis (Eoseristalis) rossica* Stackelberg, 1958**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Khlopianky env. 51.7276 N, 32.7296 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.08.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Eristalis (Eoseristalis) rupium* Fabricius, 1805**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.144 N, 24.5494 E, raised bog in *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk). Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 14.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

***Eristalis (Eoseristalis) similis* (Fallén, 1817)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskiy Park), 05.06.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 28.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 05.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 30.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 13.04.2018, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2229 N, 30.5171 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 23.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.851 N, 23.0768 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 23.04.2023, 1 ♂; 24.04.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♂; Bilasovtsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂; Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 23.04.2022, 1 ♀; 06.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Eristalis (Eristalis) tenax* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8956 E, on the garden plot, 23.08.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Khlopianky env. 51.7277 N, 32.7245 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 01.08.2024, 1 ♀; Khlopianky env. 51.7361 N, 32.7319 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 04.08.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Chernivtsi: Oselivka env. 48.4428 N, 26.5796 E, bottom of the ravine, 20.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Ivano-Frankivsk: Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6814 N, 29.7361 E, mixed forest, roadside, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6518

N, 29.5114 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 06.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.471 N, 30.2865 E, old felling in mixed forest, 19.03.2020, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rzhyschiv 49.9664 N, 31.1046 E, steppe ravine, 06.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 24.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 26.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 06.09.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Odesa: Libental env. 46.4406 N, 30.5164 E, forest shelter belt, 22.07.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Zelenivka env. 46.3046 N, 29.9972 E, steppe slopes, 23.09.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Maiaky env. 46.4123 N, 30.165 E, Dnister River floodplain, 24.09.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2938 N, 26.2891 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Khmil env. 51.4921 N, 27.2917 E, edge of the swamp (road in mixed forest between Belsk and Khmil), 20.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Ternopil: Hutysko env. 49.4039 N, 24.8315 E, meadow slopes, 16.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). Volyn: Kholopychi env. 50.8088 N, 24.7492 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.07.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6985 N, 22.4281 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 08.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank, 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonka Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6475 N, 29.4623 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 31.07.2016, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 08.09.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 27.09.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

***Eumerus amoenus* Loew, 1848**

Material examined. Kyiv: Staiky env. 50.0514 N, 30.9335 E, on the garden plot at the edge of mixed forest, 27–28.09.2023, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window, 19.08.2024, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 09.10.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Eumerus flavitarsis* Zetterstedt, 1843**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5382 N, 27.0305 E, edge of deciduous forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 06.06.2016, 1 ♂ (G. Popov); Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4963 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4168 N, 23.6768 E, mountain beech forest, 23.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Eumerus funeralis* Megerle in Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskiy Park), 02.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Dibrova env.

50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 30.07.2006, 1 ♂; 03.05.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Staiky env. 50.0514 N, 30.9335 E, on the garden plot at the edge of mixed forest, 28.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 25.07.2018, 1 ♀; 06.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4719 E, on the garden plot, 08.08.2020, 1 ♂; 24.05.2021, 1 ♂; 20.08.2021, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window), 04.09.2023, 1 ♀; 21.08.2024, 1 ♀; 26.08.2024, 1 ♀; 28.08.2024, 1 ♀; 30.08.2024, 1 ♀; 06.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Sumy, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eumerus ornatus Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 06–15.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6932 N, 22.4332 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eumerus ovatus Loew, 1848

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5046 N, 30.297 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 21.05.2010, 1 ♂; 18.06.2010, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env., 30.05.2011, 1 ♂ (M. Nesterov); Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 23.05.2012, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Divychyky env. 50.0441 N, 31.273 E, grasses in the depressions of the sandy arena of the Dnipro River left bank), 03.07.2021, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window), 06.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eumerus pauper Becker, 1921

Material examined. Kherson: Heroiske env. 46.4577 N, 31.988 E, steppe (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve, Solenoozernyi part), 11.08.2015, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson. **Zones:** Steppe.

Eumerus sogdianus Stackelberg, 1952

Material examined. Kherson: Oleshky, 02.09.2013, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Kyiv:** Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Poltava:** Poltava env., 23.06.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson, Kyiv, Poltava. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eumerus strigatus (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Kyiv: Khodosivka, 06.06.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2826 N, 26.2984 E, meadows along channel amid thickets of bushes), 16.05.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Nazarenko); Sarny env. 51.3204 N, 26.6714 E, strip of meadow vegetation near deciduous forest, 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 26.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Ternopil:** Mysyky env. 50.1044 N, 25.4881 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Ternopil. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eumerus tarsalis Loew, 1848

Material examined. AR Krym: Karabi-Yajla upper edge of beech forest, 25.06.1964, 1 ♂ (V. Ermolenko).

Distribution. Regions: AR Krym. **Zones:** Crimean Mountains.

Eumerus tricolor (Fabricius, 1798)

Material examined. Donetsk: Amvrosiivka env. 47.7803 N, 38.5704 E, steppe chalk ravine between forest shelter belts, 21.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Gubin). **Kherson:** Antonivka env. 46.674 N, 32.7702 E), 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). **Kyiv:** Kyiv (Pyrohiv) 50.3469 N, 30.51 E, hillside meadow, 20.06.2005, 1 ♂ (M. Nesterov); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E), 21.05.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Donetsk, Kherson, Kyiv. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eupeodes bucculatus (Rondani, 1857)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5341 N, 26.7643 E, wet meadow in the bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 11.04.2016, 1 ♂; 25.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4953 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 14.04.2024, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 21.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 26.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eupeodes corollae (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8956 E, on the garden plot, 27.05.2019, 1 ♀; Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt), 02.05.2020, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8956 E, on the garden plot, 03–04.08.2018, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8957 E, on the garden plot, 13–14.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, mountain slope at the edge of *Picea* forest, roadside with flowering *Cirsium palustre*, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kherson:** Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe), 09–15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4975 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 30.07.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 13.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5064 N, 30.2673 E, mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6386 N, 29.4961 E, mixed forest, roadside), 03.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6543 N, 29.4911 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 24.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 07.04.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.04.2023, 1 ♀; 09.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 06–15.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Illyashivka 50.2789 N, 26.2819 E, edge of deciduous forest (with overmature trees of *Tilia* sp.), 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Illyashivka 50.2798 N, 26.2886 E, on the garden plot, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Illyashivka env. 50.2828

N, 26.287 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels (at the edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Remel env. 50.7302 N, 26.3827 E, Horyn River floodplain, 14.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Khmil env. 51.4921 N, 27.2917 E, edge of the swamp (road in mixed forest between Belsk and Khmil), 20.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Sarny env. 51.3204 N, 26.6714 E, strip of meadow vegetation near deciduous forest, 27.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 13.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 27.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Volyn:** Mizh-hirya env. 50.733 N, 24.7825 E, ravine, 15.07.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 20.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream, 10.06.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7691 N, 22.7418 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 13.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6475 N, 29.4623 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 31.07.2016, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 25.04.2020, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2020, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 27.05.2020, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 03.06.2022, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4724 E, on the garden plot, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 07.07.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 11.06.2024, 1 ♂; 25.09.2024, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 19.11.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Eupeodes flaviceps (Rondani, 1857)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.5218 N, 30.5505 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 28.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 25.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia.

Eupeodes latifasciatus (Macquart, 1829)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5277 N, 26.7557 E, wet meadow, 22.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4949 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 13.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.657 N, 29.4988 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, near channel, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 09.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 20.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.632 N, 29.4842 E, clearing in mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 19.08.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River

floodplain forest, 18–24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3003 N, 26.2554 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 05.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 02.05.2022, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.4725 E, on the garden plot, 15.09.2022, 1 ♀; 21.09.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 07.04.2024, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 27.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eupeodes lundbecki (Soot-Ryen, 1946)

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 25.04.2010, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 30.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 28.04.2018, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 30.04.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eupeodes luniger (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn 51.01 N, 31.8584 E, mixed forest, 15.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Nizhyn env. 51.037 N, 31.8001 E, edge of deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Oselivka env. 48.4431 N, 26.5801 E, bottom of the ravine, near stream, 20.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1622 N, 24.5361 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Zarusliak and Pozhyzhavska Mt.), 09.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1541 N, 24.5308 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Pozhyzhavska Mt. and Zarusliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 25.04.2010, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 30.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 13.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 17.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.4964 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 29.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2779 E, edge of mixed forest along railway,

27.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 31.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 24.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6526 N, 29.4836 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 24.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.639 N, 29.4747 E, edge of mixed forest, 27.10.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 09.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4991 E, Teteriv River floodplain (near mixed forest, 25–26.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow, near mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zbuzh env. 50.9902 N, 26.3203 E, meadow (Horyn River valley), 14.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Remel env. 50.7302 N, 26.3827 E, Horyn River floodplain, 14.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Volyn:** Sirmychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♀; 11.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5223 N, 23.6836 E, swampy lake shore in *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8265 N, 23.1028 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♂; 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 24.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 29.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 03.09.2023, 1 ♀; 07.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lumshory env. 48.8036 N, 22.7621 E, edge of mixed forest (Velyke Trostya Lake), 17.05.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream, 10.06.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 26–27.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 27.04.2018, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 07.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 03.10.2021, 1 ♀; 25.04.2022, 1 ♂; 05.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window, 12.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 16.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Eupeodes nitens (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.4964 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 21.04.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 08.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Eurimyia lineata (Fabricius, 1787)

Material examined. **Khmelnyskyi:** Solobkivtsi env. 49.0979 N, 26.8912 E, pond shore, 11.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.4827 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Mosty 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytnka River bank, 13.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Khmil env. 51.4787 N, 27.3098 E, spring fen (Bile Lake bank), 13.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Sarny env. 51.3204 N, 26.6714 E, strip of meadow vegetation near deciduous forest, 27.05.2021, 2 ♂; 6 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; 13.07.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zhytomyr:** Bronyky env. 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank, 26.05.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Fagisyrphus cinctus (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 29.07.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♂; Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 14.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 01–10.05.2021, 4 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 08–15.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4005 N, 23.7927 E, road in mixed forest (over the Prislop pass), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4169 N, 23.6793 E, beech forest, along stream, 22.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Ferdinanda cuprea (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 28.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 22.08.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5093 N, 30.2773 E, mixed forest, 05.06.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♀ (G. Popov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5083 N, 30.2639 E, mixed forest along railway,

29.04.2017, 1 ♀; 01.06.2018, 1 ♀; 26.06.2018, 1 ♀; 06.07.2018, 1 ♀; 25.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6496 N, 29.5108 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♂; 06.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2863 N, 30.5528 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zakhariivka env. 50.5969 N, 31.0036 E, deciduous forest, 25.06.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 30.04.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 29.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6279 N, 29.4927 E, mixed forest, 14.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 01.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♂; 03.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Mosty env. 50.29 N, 26.19 E, deciduous forest, 23.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 07.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window, 12.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Ferdinandea ruficornis (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 12.07.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Zavorychi env. 50.6823 N, 31.0868 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7141 N, 29.7288 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 19.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5083 N, 30.2639 E, mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♂; 06.07.2018, 5 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5038 N, 30.2767 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 19.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5083 N, 30.2639 E, mixed forest along railway, 30.06.2021, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5053 N, 30.2687 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 30.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6378 N, 29.4966 E, clearing in mixed forest, 03.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 25.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Hammerschmidia ferruginea (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.037 N, 31.8001 E, edge of deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3012 N, 26.2992 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3014 N, 26.3022 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Helophilus continuus Loew, 1854

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env., 09.10.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Khodosivka 50.27 N, 30.5 E, Vita River valley, 13.10.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Helophilus hybridus Loew, 1846

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.041 N, 31.8023 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 28.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6569 N, 29.5002 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and mixed forest, 06.07.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 07.08.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4868 E, aspen grove in floodplain meadow (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Rudka env. 51.5283 N, 25.7547 E, swampy black alder forest, 12.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8258 N, 23.1018 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6475 N, 29.4623 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 31.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Helophilus pendulus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Cherkasy: Buchak Lake env. 49.8568 N, 31.4371 E, edge of deciduous forest, 10.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Chernihiv:** Nizhyn 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 26.05.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn env. 51.041 N, 31.8023 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 28.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 05.05.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0541 N, 31.9063 E, Oster River bank, 03.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Oselivka env. 48.4431 N, 26.5801 E, bottom of the ravine, near stream, 20.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 23.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6835 N, 29.7106 E, wet glades in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 25.04.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5207 N, 30.2713 E, Irpin River floodplain meadow, 23.08.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2921 N, 30.555 E, crossroads in deciduous forest, 07.08.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.04.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4976 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 24.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, road in mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2969 N, 26.2389 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2938 N, 26.2891 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed

forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.5283 N, 25.7547 E, swampy black alder forest, 12.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; Rudka env. 51.4789 N, 25.6854 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khmil env. 51.4781 N, 27.3081 E, mixed forest among spring fens (Bile Lake bank), 20.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 10.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). **Zhytomyr:** Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Cherkasy, Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Helophilus trivittatus (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 23.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Kherson:** Heroiske env. 46.4574 N, 31.973 E, steppe (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve), 11.08.2015, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E), 14.05.2020, 1 ♂; 25.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4971 N, 26.6508 E, grassy slopes (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6814 N, 29.7361 E, mixed forest, roadside, 09.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4705 N, 30.2872 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5146 N, 30.5446 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 18.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2915 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Balyko-Shchuchynka env. 49.9624 N, 31.1191 E, ravine in deciduous forest, 05.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Ukrainka env. 50.1561 N, 30.7317 E, mixed forest, 14.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4991 E, Teteriv River floodplain (near mixed forest, 25–26.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2821 E, edge of mixed forest, 13.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2977 N, 26.2638 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khmil env. 51.4921 N, 27.2917 E, edge of the swamp (road in mixed forest between Belsk and Khmil), 20.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Kholopychi env. 50.8088 N, 24.7492 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.07.2019, 1 ♂; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 20.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 27.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 06.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Zaporizhya:** Yuryivka env. 46.6071 N, 35.1564 E, steppe ravine), 11.09.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov). **Zhytomyr:** Zelena Poliana env. 50.6001 N, 28.1255 E, mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zaporizhya, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Heringia heringi (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Kukshin env. 51.176 N, 31.632 E, edge of deciduous forest, 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 25.04.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2936 N, 30.5531 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env.

50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 06.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀; Kodra env. 50.6318 N, 29.4851 E, felling in mixed forest, 05.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08–13.05.2020, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Ischiodon scutellaris (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Kherson: Heroiske env. 46.4574 N, 31.973 E, steppe (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve), 10.08.2015, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson. **Zones:** Steppe.

Lapposyrphus lapponicus (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5028 N, 30.2848 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.03.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.465 N, 30.6741 E, Lisove Lake shore), 08.04.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 06–11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀; Mereshor env. 48.4126 N, 23.6832 E, Tereblia River bank, meadow near stream), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5241 N, 23.672 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5223 N, 23.6836 E, swampy lake shore in *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 10.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, mountain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 23.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polynyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18–19.07.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 17.04.2023, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 21.04.2023, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 09.06.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Lejogaster metallina (Fabricius, 1777)

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 28.05.2006, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 30.06.2006, 1 ♀; 07.07.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Rivne: Velyka Lyubasha 50.9549 N, 26.365 E, wet meadow (Zamchisko River valley), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Lejogaster tarsata (Meigerle in Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv (Pyrohiv) 50.3469 N, 30.51 E, hillside meadow, 21.06.2005, 1 ♀ (M. Nesterov); Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 30.06.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 27.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.51 N, 33.95 E, 23.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Ternopil:** Synkiv env. 48.6211 N, 25.9913 E, Dnister River left bank, steppe slopes, 16.07.2016, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Zhytomyr:** Bronyky env. 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank, 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Sumy, Ternopil, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Lejops vittatus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 21.05.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Lejota ruficornis (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5034 N, 30.2798 E, mixed forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6947 N, 22.4324 E, felling in deciduous forest, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (G. Popov); Pashkivtsi env. 48.81 N, 22.8676 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Leucozона (Ischyrosyrphus) glaucia (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Leucozона (Ischyrosyrphus) laternaria (Müller, 1776)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Shparyk). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2966 N, 26.2624 E, road in mixed forest near Zbytynka River floodplain, 13.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2976 N, 26.2635 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2976 N, 26.2785 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 16.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8367 N, 23.1224 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 22.06.2023, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.07.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Leucozона (Leucozона) inopinata Doczkal, 2000

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Leucozона (Leucozона) lucorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 28.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Vorokhta env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 10.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3015 N, 26.3018 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Novomalyn env. 50.2852 N, 26.3652 E, mixed forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4295 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Mallota fuciformis (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8527 N, 23.0789 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 06–07.05.2017, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Mallota megilliformis (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 12.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 27.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♂; 23.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂; 04.06.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4897 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Mallota tricolor Loew, 1871

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0482 N, 31.8712 E, wet meadow (Oster River bank), 28.05.2021, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Bernove env. 48.486 N, 26.6508 E, edge of deciduous planting (Dnister River valley), 22.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.33 N, 30.61 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Zhukiv Is. on Dnipro River), 29.05.2013, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 21.06.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 31.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); 06.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 04.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4697 N, 30.4081 E, inside the house (on the balcony), 05.06.2022, 1 ♀ (B. Vasko); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Matsumyia berberina (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1400–1500 m a.s.l., 29.07.2008, 1 ♀ (K. Martynova). **Kyiv:** Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♂; 08.06.2022, 1

♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3015 N, 26.2995 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 2 ♂; 5 ♀; 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskiy Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.81 N, 22.8676 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.06.2024, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Megasyrphus erraticus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.158 N, 24.5282 E, swampy meadow slope in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyina-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Melangyna compositarum (Verrall, 1873)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Melangyna lasiophthalma (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 08.04.2007, 1 ♀; 05.04.2009, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4646 N, 30.3245 E, wasteland at the edge of mixed forest, 30.03.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.03.2019, 4 ♂; 2 ♀; 08.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5082 N, 30.2636 E, mixed forest along railway, 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.471 N, 30.2865 E, old felling in mixed forest, 19.03.2020, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 09.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5028 N, 30.2849 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 10.04.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 12.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6504 N, 29.5102 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.04.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6524 N, 29.5118 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv

River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀; 14.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 20.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 10–13.04.2018, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 14.04.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Melangyna lucifera Nielsen, 1980

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylyvka env. 50.9689 N, 31.8613 E, edge of mixed forest, 31.03.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 05.04.2009, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.4208 N, 30.4933 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), roadside), 29.03.2017, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 10.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 17.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.03.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.471 N, 30.2865 E, old felling in mixed forest, 19.03.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 19.04.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5028 N, 30.2849 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01–06.04.2021, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4224 N, 30.4946 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), 19–26.03.2007, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 27.03.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Melangyna quadrimaculata (Verrall, 1873)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3515 N, 30.4815 E, wasteland (Theophania Park env.), 28.03.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

Melangyna umbellatarum (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 08.08.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, Esman River valley, 02.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Sumy. **Zones:** Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Melanogaster arosa (Loew, 1843)

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6576 N, 29.4991 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 16.05.2015, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀. **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♂; 4 ♀. **Zhytomyr:** Berezova Hat env. 50.4707 N, 28.1185 E, wet meadows among shrubs (Tnia River valley), 26.05.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Bronyky env. 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank), 26.05.2021, 3 ♂; 1 ♀.

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

Melanogaster jaroslavensis (Stackelberg, 1922)

Material examined. Sumy: Matskove env. 51.493 N, 33.903 E, Esman River valley, 10–15.05.2018, 2 ♂; 2 ♀.

Distribution. Regions: Sumy. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

Melanogaster nuda (Macquart, 1829)

Material examined. **Chernivtsi:** Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 2 ♂; 3 ♀. **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3414 N, 30.4885 E, city park (Theophania Park), 21.05.2013, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5095 N, 30.2629 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂; Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E, 01.06.2018, 1 ♀; 19–22.05.2018, 2 ♂; 3 ♀; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4706 N, 30.2904 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂. **Rivne:** Ilyyashivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 4 ♂; 9 ♀; Mosty 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 13.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3003 N, 26.2554 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Ilyyashivka env. 50.2833 N, 26.2936 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels (at the edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 2 ♂; 3 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2785 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Novomalyn env. 50.2919 N, 26.3695 E, reservoir shore (Zbytynka River bank, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Mosty 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀; Velyka Lyubasha 50.9549 N, 26.365 E, wet meadow (Zamchisko River valley), 27.05.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12–15.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17–19.05.2019, 2 ♂; 2 ♀. **Zakarpatska:** Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 2 ♂; 4 ♀. **Zhytomyr:** Berezova Hat env. 50.4707 N, 28.1185 E, wet meadows among shrubs (Tnia River valley), 26.05.2021, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Melanogaster parumplicata (Loew, 1840)

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5025 N, 30.2829 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 05.05.2016, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀. **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Velyka Lyubasha 50.9549 N, 26.365 E, wet meadow (Zamchisko River valley), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; 4 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17–22.05.2019, 4 ♂; 7 ♀. **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 07.05.2017, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Melanostoma mellinum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Morivsk 51.0883 N, 30.8823 E, on the garden plot, 11.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Chernivtsi:** Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lenkivtsi env. 48.5341 N, 26.7643 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lenkivtsi env. 48.5378 N, 26.7609 E, grassy slopes in deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1558 N, 24.5342 E, mountain meadow with flowering *Senecio* sp. at the upper edge of *Picea* forest, 09.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4975 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 30.07.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Leonivka env. 50.787 N, 29.9195 E, felling in mixed forest, 16.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A.

Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 07.08.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4964 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Balyko-Shchuchynka env. 49.9624 N, 31.1191 E, ravine in deciduous forest, 05.08.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5021 N, 30.2828 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4963 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4976 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 18.10.2022, 1 ♂; Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 08.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4868 E, aspen grove in floodplain meadow (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂. **Rivne:** Ilyyashivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3003 N, 26.2554 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 18.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; Berezhnytsia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Hlynne env. 51.5633 N, 27.4292 E, Stvyha River bank, 20.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.5952 N, 27.0902 E, meadows among thickets of woody vegetation, 21.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀. **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 13.07.2018, 1 ♀. **Ternopil:** Hutysko env. 49.4039 N, 24.8315 E, meadow slopes, 16.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.6999 N, 22.4319 E, mountain meadow, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 17.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4078 N, 23.6899 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8407 N, 23.0491 E, edge of mixed forest, along stream, 21.04.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream, 10.06.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7803 N, 22.7598 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 13.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6475 N, 29.4623 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 31.07.2016, 1 ♂; Ukrainka env. 50.7607 N, 29.4129 E, Irsha River floodplain meadow, 17.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.4725 E, on the garden plot, 11.10.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 09.10.2024, 1 ♂; 13.10.2024, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Ternopil, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Melanostoma scalare (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Nizhyn 51.01 N, 31.8584 E, mixed forest, 15.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn env. 51.041 N, 31.8023 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 28.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrabskyi Park), 28.04.2024, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8957 E, on the garden plot, 13–14.07.2023, 1 ♀; 27–28.06.2024, 1 ♂. **Chernivtsi:** Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♂. **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, mountain slope at the edge of *Picea* forest, roadside with flowering *Cirsium palustre*, 11.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Khmelnitskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.5397 E, deciduous forest, 22.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka

River floodplain forest, 25.06.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 19.07.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2781 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2237 N, 30.5193 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 11.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 25.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs), 05.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Ilyyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Novomalyn 50.2919 N, 26.3695 E, Zbytynka River bank, meadow, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Ilyyashivka env. 50.2783 N, 26.281 E, edge of deciduous forest, 14.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Simyichky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.81 N, 22.8676 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 04–08.05.2017, 2 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09–11.05.2017, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4169 N, 23.6793 E, beech forest, along stream, 22–23.07.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Meligramma triangulifera (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6476 N, 29.4868 E, road in mixed forest, 17.04.2017, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6512 N, 29.4917 E, road in mixed forest, 21.04.2018, 1 ♂; 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5082 N, 30.2636 E, mixed forest along railway, 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6571 N, 29.5 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest), 13.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.04.2020, 1 ♂; 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 09.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 29.04.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 09.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2876 N, 30.5524 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.06.2022, 1 ♀; 14.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 20.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, edge of mixed forest, 04.09.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env.

48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 05.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Meliscaeva auricollis (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0114 N, 31.8755 E, roadside), 06.04.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 17.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 27.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 08.04.2019, 1 ♀; 10–13.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♂; 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 25.05.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 25.05.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 18.06.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Meliscaeva cinctella (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonia Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7989 N, 22.8001 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 18.07.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 10.10.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Merodon aberrans Egger, 1860

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3964 N, 30.5447 E, grassy slopes (Lysa Hora), 04.07.2013, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 23.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Merodon analis Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8273 N, 23.1051 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 26.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20–21.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Merodon armipes Rondani, 1843

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5378 N, 26.7609 E, grassy slopes in deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Khmelnytskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4971 N, 26.6508 E, grassy slopes (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov & V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

***Merodon avidus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined. Odesa: Zelenivka env. 46.3046 N, 29.9972 E, steppe slopes, 23.09.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Odesa. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Merodon cinereus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhavska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 27.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Vorokhta env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1514 N, 24.5373 E, mountain meadow, southern slope (Pozhyzhavska Mt.), 11.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1551 N, 24.5354 E, mountain meadow, near house (Pozhyzhavska Mt.), 14.08.2023, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Merodon equestris* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hraskyi Park), 10.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 21.05.2019, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0482 N, 31.8712 E, wet meadow (Oster River bank), 28.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0485 N, 31.9012 E, wet meadow (Oster River bank), 14.06.2021, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.4612 N, 30.6044 E, city park, 15.05.2013, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4728 N, 30.3199 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4323 N, 30.4952 E, Batiyva Mt.), 30.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Gezun). **Rivne:** Sarny env. 51.3178 N, 26.6339 E, Sluch River bank), 28.05.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.296 N, 26.2809 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest (Zbytynka River bank, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4082 N, 23.6731 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolo-chava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 22.07.2022, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4087 N, 23.6866 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 22.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Bilasovytzia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 5 ♂; 1 ♀; Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 4 ♂; 2 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 21.05.2023, 1 ♀; 29.05.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂; 06.06.2024, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 05–06.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Merodon moenium* Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Kyiv: Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2189 N, 30.5199 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 05.07.2017, 1 ♂; 13.07.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

***Merodon nigritarsis* Rondani, 1845**

Material examined. AR Krym: Borysivka env. 45.1 N, 36.23 E, steppe (Kerch Peninsula, 6 km N, Opuk Mt.), 08.06.1960, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Ermolenko).

Distribution. Regions: AR Krym. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Merodon pruni* (Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined. AR Krym: Borysivka env. 45.1 N, 36.23 E, steppe (Kerch Peninsula, 6 km N, Opuk Mt.), 08.06.1960, 1 ♂ (V. Ermolenko).

Distribution. Regions: AR Krym. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Merodon ruficornis* Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka & A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary), 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 3 ♂; 2 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 03.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rzhyschiv 49.975 N, 31.1052 E, deciduous forest, 21.05.2021, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytzia env. 48.6959 N, 22.4317 E, Uzh River valley), 03–06.05.2017, 4 ♂; 3 ♀; Kamianytzia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 07–09.05.2017, 6 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Merodon rufus* Meigen, 1838**

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5088 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 05–11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Merodon serrulatus* Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Donetsk: Samsonove env. 47.2964 N, 38.1883 E, steppe ravine with *Prunus spinosa* (Khomutovska Step Reserve), 06–07.06.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Gubin).

Distribution. Regions: Donetsk. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Mesembrius peregrinus* (Loew, 1846)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0482 N, 31.8712 E, wet meadow (Oster River bank), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2873 N, 30.556 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 06.06.2016, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (G. Popov & A. Prokhorov); 24.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5042 N, 30.2829 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6578 N, 29.4993 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 03.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Mosty 50.3048 N, 26.1932 E, roadside), 13.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Microdon analis* (Macquart, 1842)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary), 26.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.46 N, 30.54 E, Trukhaniv Is. on Dnipro River), 01.06.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.4224 N, 30.4946 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), 30.05.2007, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.46 N, 30.54 E, Trukhaniv Is. on Dnipro River), 29.05.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2931 N, 30.5519 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 10.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2832 N, 26.2825 E, road in mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2977 N, 26.2399 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2993 N, 26.2702 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Zelena Poliana env. 50.6001 N, 28.1255 E, mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Microdon devius* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.0464 N, 31.7972 E, glade in mixed forest, 03.06.2019, 1 ♀; Nizhynske env. 50.9875 N, 31.8022 E, wet meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2022, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0485 N, 31.8717 E, pond shore, 06.06.2023, 1 ♂; Nizhynske env. 50.9882 N, 31.8012 E, wet meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 01.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2872 N, 30.5552 E, edge of deciduous forest, 06.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2177 N, 30.5226 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 05.07.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 08–15.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3015 N, 26.2861 E, roadside, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 17.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2973 N, 26.2786 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2993 N, 26.2702 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 16–17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Microdon mutabilis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhynske env. 50.9852 N, 31.7919 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.06.2019, 1 ♂; Nizhynske env. 50.9881 N, 31.8011 E, wet meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 19.06.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv (Pyrohiv) 50.34 N, 30.52 E, 20.05.2013, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 21.05.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E, 21.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Microdon myrmicae* Schönrogge, Barr, Wardlaw, Napper, Gardner, Breen, Elmes & Thomas, 2002**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5506 N, 27.0285 E, upper edge of hornbeam-oak forest (Polyvaniv Yar), 25.05.2022, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2977 N, 26.2403 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♂; 15.06.2021, 1 ♂; 16.06.2021, 1 ♂; 17.06.2021, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2993 N, 26.2702 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂; 16.06.2021, 1 ♀; 17.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2973 N, 26.2786 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

***Myathropa florea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Petryliv env. 48.9897 N, 24.9866 E, roadside, 17.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀; Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6283 N, 29.4917 E, mixed forest, 23.09.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 27.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4706 N, 30.2902 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov);

Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Balyko-Shchuchynka env. 49.9624 N, 31.1191 E, ravine in deciduous forest, 05.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kotsiubynske env. 50.473 N, 30.2897 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 18.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6557 N, 29.4931 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 14.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4868 E, aspen grove in floodplain meadow (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Karolino-Bugaz 46.1643 N, 30.5631 E, sandy seashore, 23.07.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3061 N, 26.2435 E, edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 15.04.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

***Myolepta dubia* (Fabricius, 1805)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Kyiv 50.4224 N, 30.4946 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), 17.06.2010, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Myolepta obscura* Becher, 1882**

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.7004 N, 22.4391 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Myolepta vara* (Panzer, 1798)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env., 50.4713° N, 30.2993° E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♀; 13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov leg.); Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env.: 48.7007° N, 22.4384° E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (G. Popov leg.); 11.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov leg.); 48.6983° N, 22.4306° E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov leg.).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

***Neoascia (Neoascia) annexa* (Müller, 1776)**

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4169 N, 23.6793 E, beech forest, along stream, 23.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Neoascia (Neoascia) podagrica* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8956 E, on the garden plot, 04.05.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 27.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6537 N, 29.4863 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along channel), 02.09.2023, 1 ♀; Ulianyky env. 49.9141 N, 31.1229 E, meadow along stream on the bottom of the ravine, 27.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6911 N, 22.458 E,

deciduous forest, 08–10.06.2018, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 01.10.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Neoscia (Neoscia) tenur (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 08.05.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.04.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 02.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀; 08.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.4789 N, 25.6854 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.6748 N, 27.114 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 15–17.06.2021, 2 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zhytomyr:** Berezova Hat env. 50.4707 N, 28.1185 E, wet meadows among shrubs (Tnia River valley), 26.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6467 N, 29.4714 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 25.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Neoscia (Neosciella) interrupta (Megerle in Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4976 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 21.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 22.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4974 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 24.04.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 22.04.2021, 1 ♂; 28.04.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀; 10.05.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527

N, 29.4843 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the channel), 13.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 08.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Neoscia (Neosciella) meticulosa (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5006 N, 30.2847 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6835 N, 29.7106 E, wet glades in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5058 N, 30.2688 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 27.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.04.2019, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4974 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2876 N, 30.5524 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 25.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 01–02.05.2021, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Illyashivka env. 50.27 N, 26.32 E, deciduous forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 03.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Neoscia (Neosciella) obliqua Coe, 1940

Material examined. **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 04.05.2017, 1 ♀ (G. Popov); Ly-povets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Neocnemodon brevidens (Egger, 1865)

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 02.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 27.07.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.5218 N, 30.5505 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 28.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♀; 01.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Kocher-gy env. 51.478 N, 33.8779 E, 09.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 21.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Neocnemodon latitarsis* (Egger, 1865)**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 16.10.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 27.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 22.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 14.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 20.04.2024, 1 ♂; Kodra env. 50.6367 N, 29.4746 E, road in mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 13.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Neocnemodon pubescens* (Deelucchi & Pschorn-Walcher, 1955)**

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

***Neocnemodon verrucula* (Collin, 1931)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4976 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 21.04.2018, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6555 N, 29.4953 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Neocnemodon vitripennis* (Meigen, 1822)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Kyiv (mixed forest (Mykil's'kyi Lis), 08.05.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 10.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 10.07.2023, 1 ♂; 14.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Kochergy env. 51.478 N, 33.8779 E, 09.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

***Orthonevra brevicornis* (Loew, 1843)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest,

16.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀; 08.05.2022, 1 ♀; 10.05.2022, 6 ♂; 2 ♀; 14.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 19.04.2023, 1 ♂; 29.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 02.05.2023, 1 ♀; 06.05.2023, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 12.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4925 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03–04.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28–29.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀; Velyka Lyubasha 50.9549 N, 26.365 E, wet meadow (Zamchisko River valley), 27.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia.

***Orthonevra elegans* (Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5042 N, 30.2853 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 11.07.2010, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Orthonevra erythrogonia* (Malm, 1863)**

Material examined. Sumy: Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 16.07.2018, 1 ♀; 10–15.05.2018, 4 ♂; 2 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Sumy. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

***Orthonevra geniculata* (Meigen, 1830)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 03.05.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 2 ♂; 2 ♀; 16.05.2021, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 06.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 10.05.2022, 1 ♀; 14.05.2022, 1 ♀; 22.04.2023, 1 ♀; 29.04.2023, 4 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 01.05.2023, 1 ♀; 06.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 06.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 20.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Orthonevra incisa* (Loew, 1843)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Orthonevra intermedia* Lundbeck, 1916**

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5025 N, 30.2829 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 26.06.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4922 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 24.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.07.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6526 N, 29.4836 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.07.2023, 1 ♂; 19.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 29.05.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs, 05.07.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4868 E, aspen grove in floodplain meadow (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4865 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 05.07.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Rudka env. 51.4849 N, 25.7068 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Orthonevra nobilis* (Fallén, 1817)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 07.07.2006, 1 ♀; 04.08.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). Ternopil: Beremyany env. 48.8694 N, 25.4196 E, Strypa River mouth, 20.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Ternopil. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

***Paragus (Pandasyopthalmus) constrictus* Šimić, 1986**

Material examined. Kyiv: Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 27–28.04.2024, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6408 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 12.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Paragus (Pandasyopthalmus) haemorrhous* Megerle in Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Morivsk 51.1159 N, 30.8747 E, edge of mixed forest, 10.07.2020, 4 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kherson: Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe), 09–15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2792 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.219 N, 30.5207 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, meadow slope with flowering *Origanum vulgare*, 03.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6468 N, 29.5164 E, road in mixed forest, 14.08.2021, 1 ♂; Kodra env. 50.632 N, 29.4845 E, clearing in mixed forest, 08.07.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6576 N, 29.4955 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 02.09.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 11.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Staiky env. 50.0514 N, 30.9335 E, on the garden plot at the edge of mixed forest, 28.09.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6333 N, 29.4817 E, road in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 16.06.2022, 1 ♀; 11.06.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

***Paragus (Pandasyopthalmus) tibialis* (Fallén, 1817)**

Material examined. Kherson: Pavlivka env. 46.2386 N, 33.8132 E, steppe), 13.09.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Strohanivka env. 46.2386 N, 33.8132 E, steppe areas along Sivash Gulf, 03.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Mar-

tynov). Zaporizhya: Yuryivka env. 46.6071 N, 35.1564 E, steppe ravine), 11.09.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Martynov).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson, Zaporizhya. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) albifrons* (Fallén, 1817)**

Material examined. Kherson: Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe), 09–15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Kodra env. 50.6323 N, 29.4829 E, felling in mixed forest, 01.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 22.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) bicolor* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined. Kherson: Heroiske env. (steppe (Black Sea Biosphere Reserve), 15.08.2015, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe), 09–15.05.2020, 27 ♂; 3 ♀ (R. Mishustin).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) bradescui* Stănescu, 1981**

Material examined. Kherson: Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E), 25.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) compeditus* Wiedemann, 1830**

Material examined. Kherson: Strohanivka env. 46.2386 N, 33.8132 E, steppe areas along Sivash Gulf, 03.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) finitimus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1971**

Material examined. Kyiv: Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5217 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, upper part of the meadow slopes), 25.07.2021, 1 ♂; Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2241 N, 30.5198 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields), 03.08.2021, 1 ♂; Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.219 N, 30.5207 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, meadow slope with flowering *Origanum vulgare*, 03.08.2021, 1 ♂; 11.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) flammeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1971**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Morivsk env. 51.1159 N, 30.8747 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.07.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4709 N, 30.2873 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.632 N, 29.4845 E, clearing in mixed forest, 03.07.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6333 N, 29.4817 E, road in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, 4 ♂; 3 ♀; 03.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6352 N, 29.4774 E, felling in mixed forest, 17.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4725 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 14.05.2024, 1 ♂; 16.05.2024, 1 ♂; 01.06.2024, 1 ♂; 04.06.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Paragus (Paragus) hyalopteri* Marcos-García & Rojo, 1994**

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4964 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 10.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Paragus (Paragus) otenicus* Stănescu, 1977**

Material examined. Kherson: Pavlivka env. 46.2386 N, 33.8132 E, steppe), 13.09.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe), 09–15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson. **Zones:** Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) pecchiolii* Rondani, 1857**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt), 02.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Morivsk 51.1159 N, 30.8747 E, edge of mixed forest, 10.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2973 N, 30.5443 E, glade in deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 11–13.05.2019, 3 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 06.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. (deciduous forest, 06.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. (road in mixed forest, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.08.2016, 1 ♂; 25.06.2017, 1 ♂; 23.07.2020, 1 ♂; 23.07.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7145 N, 29.7283 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 19.07.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 20.07.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2973 N, 30.5443 E, glade in deciduous forest, 10.08.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4709 N, 30.2873 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2876 N, 30.5524 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.473 N, 30.2897 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mryhy env. 50.2652 N, 30.5651 E, meadow, 04.07.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.08.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Nova Buda env. 50.6913 N, 29.7083 E, clearing in mixed forest, 07.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 14.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.08.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6514 N, 29.4921 E, road in mixed forest, 02.09.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♂; 30.06.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 30.06.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.08.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 31.08.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Poltava: Poltava env., 23.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Rivne: Illyashivka env. 50.2798 N, 26.2711 E, edge of mixed forest and old overgrown felling), 14.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytisia env. 48.69 N, 22.43 E, deciduous forest, 08–09.06.2018, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 09–11.05.2017, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Poltava, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Paragus (Paragus) quadrifasciatus* Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Kyiv: Khodosivka 50.27 N, 30.5 E, meadow slope), 28.04.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.3964 N, 30.5447 E, Lysa Hora), 11.09.2015, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E), 22.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6556 N, 29.4968 E, mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 25.08.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 26.06.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 13.05.2024, 1 ♂; 14.05.2024, 1 ♀; 17.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Parasyrphus lineola* (Zetterstedt, 1843)**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.165 N, 24.5364 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest (Zarosliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.158 N, 24.5282 E, swampy meadow slope in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 12.08.2023, 1 ♀; 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonja Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Kolochava env. 48.405 N, 23.7927 E, road in mixed forest (over the Prislup pass), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Parasyrphus malinellus* (Collin, 1952)**

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Parasyrphus nigratarsis* (Zetterstedt, 1843)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 10.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 22.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 09.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytisia env. 48.699 N, 22.4294 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

***Parasyrphus punctulatus* (Verrall, 1873)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Yarok env. 48.6691 N, 22.4866 E, edge of deciduous forest (?Antalovska polyana?), 08.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8258 N, 23.1018 E, edge of mixed forest, 05.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

***Parasyrphus relictus* (Zetterstedt, 1838)**

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyina-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Parhelophilus consimilis* (Malm, 1863)**

Material examined. Rivne: Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7086 E, swamp), 12.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Parhelophilus frutetorum* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined. Kherson: Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E), 25.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 02.06.2016, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 06.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env.

50.5027 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.06.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 06.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5027 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 19.06.2020, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 14.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, road in mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 2 ♂; 2 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2969 N, 26.2389 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3013 N, 26.2997 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Parhelophilus versicolor (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0541 N, 31.9063 E, Oster River bank, 03.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 03.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2873 N, 30.556 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 09.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 03.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7086 E, swamp, 12.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Berezhnysia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Pelecocera (Pelecocera) tricineta Hoffmannsegg in Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha 50.3088 N, 26.2405 E, strip of meadow vegetation at the edge of deciduous forest (near pond), 16.06.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Nazarenko).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

Pipiza accola Violovitsh, 1985

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.4997 N, 30.2859 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28

E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 08.04.2019, 1 ♂; 20.04.2019, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; 25.04.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2928 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 09.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4928 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6543 N, 29.4911 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 12.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 28.04.2022, 1 ♂; 30.04.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Pipiza austriaca Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Volosiv env. 48.7195 N, 24.6929 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.08.2004, 1 ♀ (G. Popov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Pipiza carbonaria Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Odesa: Budei env. 48.0434 N, 29.2318 E, waterlogged meadow at the edge of oak ravine forest, 15.05.2010, 1 ♂ (G. Popov).

Distribution. Regions: Odesa. **Zones:** Wood-and-Steppe.

Pipiza fasciata Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 02.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2928 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 17.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 11.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 27.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 03.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 03.05.2019, 1 ♀; 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 28.04.2016, 3 ♂; 2 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5008 N, 30.2747 E, Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyashivka 50.2789 N, 26.2819 E, edge of deciduous forest (with overmature trees of *Tilia* sp.), 11.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Pipiza festiva Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 02.05.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 02.08.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.4222 N, 30.4961 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), 09.08.2007, 1 ♂; 21.09.2007, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kaharlyk 49.865 N, 30.8096 E, on the garden plot, 23.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Pipiza lugubris* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined. **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Havrylivka env. 48.7081 N, 24.7104 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 16.08.2004, 1 ♂ (G. Popov). **Kyiv:** Khodosivka, 24.07.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Rivne:** Berezhnitsya env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside), 19.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 05.08.2018, 1 ♂; Kochergy env. 51.478 N, 33.8779 E), 09.08.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 10.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Pipiza luteibarba* Vujić, Radenković & Polić, 2008**

Material examined. **Chernivtsi:** Hrushivtsi env. 48.5942 N, 26.7862 E, edge of oak forest, 04.05.2008, 1 ♂ (A. Lishchuk).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

***Pipiza luteitarsis* Zetterstedt, 1843**

Material examined. **Donetsk:** Donetsk 48.0122 N, 37.8757 E, Donetsk Botanical garden), 27.04.2005, 1 ♂; 11.05.2005, 1 ♂ (G. Popov). **Kyiv:** Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 09.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4925 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 08.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Donetsk, Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Steppe.

***Pipiza noctiluca* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. **Chernihiv:** Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 27.04.2019, 1 ♂; Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt), 02.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2928 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); 29.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 29.07.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.04.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 08.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 03.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀; 03.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17–18.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 24.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 05.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 08.05.2017, 1 ♂; 09–11.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Pipiza notata* Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀; 03.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E), 22.05.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6456 N, 29.5151 E, road in mixed forest, 27.07.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Pipiza quadrimaculata* (Panzer, 1802)**

Material examined. **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Kosiv env. 48.2899 N, 25.115 E, oak-hornbeam forest with *Picea*), 13.06.2005, 1 ♀ (V. Rizun). **Zakarpatska:** Synevrska Poliana env. 48.6176 N, 23.6807 E, Synevyr Lake shore), 15.06.2005, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Pipizella annulata* (Macquart, 1829)**

Material examined. **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5048 N, 30.2736 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 25.06.2017, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5042 N, 30.2829 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 19.06.2020, 1 ♂; 20.06.2020, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; 24.06.2020, 1 ♀; 30.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Pipizella divicoi* (Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1974)**

Material examined. **Rivne:** Mosty env. 50.2755 N, 26.2019 E, glades in oak-hornbeam forest, 13.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Nazarenko); Buderazh env. 50.3189 N, 26.15 E, meadow slopes), 23.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

***Pipizella viduata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. **Chernivtsi:** Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lenkivtsi env. 48.5188 N, 26.7912 E, bottom of the ravine, along stream (Sursha River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary), 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2177 N, 30.5226 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 05.07.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2965 N, 30.5345 E, roadside at the edge of deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 10.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2187 N, 30.5207 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (meadow slope near bottom of the ravine), 11.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Buderazh env. 50.3189 N, 26.15 E, meadow slopes), 23.05.2019, 1 ♂; Zbuzh env. 50.9902 N, 26.3203 E, meadow (Horyn River valley), 14.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Zbuzh env. 50.988 N, 26.3262 E, edge of mixed forest (Horyn River bank), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 05.05.2017, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.701 N, 22.4368 E, edge of deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4078 N, 23.6899 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Berezova Hat env. 50.4707 N, 28.1185 E, wet meadows among shrubs (Tnia River valley), 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Pipizella virens* (Fabricius, 1805)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 22.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Hrushiv env. 49.9 N, 31.2 E), 01.06.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Platycheirus albimanus* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 04.05.2018, 1 ♂; 10.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.514 N, 26.7955 E, deciduous forest, along stream (Sursha River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary), 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1622 N, 24.5361 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Zarusliak and Pohyzhevska Mt.), 09.08.2023, 1 ♂; Vorokhta env. 48.1558 N, 24.5342 E, mountain meadow with flowering *Senecio* sp. at the upper edge of *Picea* forest, 09.08.2023, 1 ♂; Vorokhta env. 48.1578 N, 24.5306 E, edge of *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; 6 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂; 13.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.158 N, 24.5282 E, swampy meadow slope in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Khmelnytskyi: Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5021 N, 30.2795 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 01.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 25.04.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyshyivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels), 10.05.2018, 1 ♀; Ilyshyivka env. 50.2829 N, 26.2874 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels (at the edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4078 N, 23.6899 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀; Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5223 N, 23.6836 E, swampy lake shore in *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♂; Bilasovytzia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 09.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 06.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Polianska Huta env. 48.7481 N, 22.7714 E, deciduous forest, 18.05.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream), 10.06.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂; 2 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7989 N, 22.8001 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 18.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Platycheirus ambiguus* (Fallén, 1817)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2196 N, 30.5208 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 23.04.2018, 1 ♂; Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2143 N, 30.5268 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 23.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8326 N, 23.1009 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Zhytomyr: Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N,

29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 21.04.2021, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2021, 1 ♀; 04.05.2021, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 02.05.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4724 E, on the garden plot, 05.05.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 08.05.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 13.04.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 13.04.2023, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 17.04.2023, 15 ♂; 6 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 25.04.2023, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6408 N, 29.4719 E, on the garden plot, 08.05.2023, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 30.03.2024, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 05.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Platycheirus angustatus* (Zetterstedt, 1843)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5367 N, 27.0298 E, meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, near stream), 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov). Khmelnytskyi: Dubivka env. 49.1327 N, 26.4427 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.08.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.06.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 25.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.51 N, 30.2622 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 2 ♂; 3 ♀; 25.04.2019, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 18–23.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4965 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 02.08.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 09.08.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4972 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♀; Rudka env. 51.4789 N, 25.6854 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.298 N, 26.2768 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 16.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 25.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 04.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Platycheirus clypeatus* (Meigen, 1822)**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, swampy meadow at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 11.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Buscha env. 50.3003 N, 26.2554 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 18.05.2019, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.6748 N, 27.114 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, Esman River valley, 25.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Platycheirus europaeus* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990**

Material examined. Kyiv: Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Platycheirus fulviventris* (Macquart, 1829)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 01.06.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5277 N, 26.7557 E, wet meadow, 22.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.5367 N, 27.0298 E, meadow along the Dnister River

tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, near stream), 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov & A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Khodosivka env. 50.2642 N, 30.5317 E, meadow, 28.04.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4965 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 30.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4974 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4964 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.06.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 09.08.2020, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 29.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 2 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5021 N, 30.2828 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.08.2021, 1 ♀; 08.09.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6547 N, 29.4919 E, Teteriv River floodplain (wet meadows among thickets of shrubs), 04.05.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6559 N, 29.4936 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 24.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4843 E, grassy vegetation on the bank of the channel, 19.08.2024, 1 ♀; 24.08.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 19.08.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04–10.05.2020, 1 ♀; 18–23.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyshivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2985 N, 26.2785 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytnyka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2947 N, 26.2873 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 17.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hlynye env. 51.5633 N, 27.4292 E, Stvyha River bank, 20.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀; Zbuzh env. 50.988 N, 26.3262 E, edge of mixed forest (Horyn River bank), 27.05.2021, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀; Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnyka River floodplain meadow, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Platycheirus manicatus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Platycheirus occultus Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach and Speight, 1990

Material examined. Khmelnytskyi: Dubivka env. 49.1327 N, 26.4427 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.08.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5097 N, 30.2623 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 11.04.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2136 N, 30.5276 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 23.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.04.2018, 1 ♀; 01.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A.

Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Murromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.04.2019, 1 ♀; 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.51 N, 30.2622 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 25.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6568 N, 29.4974 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 13.04.2020, 7 ♂; 1 ♀; 17.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6571 N, 29.5 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 13.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2795 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5027 N, 30.2838 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 20.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 05.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.657 N, 29.5001 E, roadside (near Teteriv River floodplain, 10.05.2021, 1 ♀; Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades with *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4976 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 23.08.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.04.2024, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6539 N, 29.4861 E, dry meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂; Kodra env. 50.6288 N, 29.4907 E, road in mixed forest, 07.07.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4843 E, grassy vegetation on the bank of the channel, 19.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17–24.04.2020, 4 ♂; 7 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Platycheirus parmatus Rondani, 1857

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lumshory env. 48.8036 N, 22.7621 E, edge of mixed forest (Velyke Trostya Lake), 17.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 04–08.05.2017, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Platycheirus peltatus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Khmelnytskyi: Kamianets-Podilskyi env. 48.6389 N, 26.5742 E, edge of oak-hornbeam forest, 27.07.2005, 1 ♀ (A. Lishchuk). **Rivne:** Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banych env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, Esman River valley, 25.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Khmelnytskyi, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Platycheirus perpallidus Verrall, 1901

Material examined. Rivne: Hrabun env. 51.5374 N, 27.1881 E, raised bog, 29.05.2021, 1 ♂ (M. Franchuk).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

Platycheirus scutatus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 05.05.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Morivsk 51.0883 N, 30.8823 E, on the garden plot, 10.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nizhyn

50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env. 48.5256 N, 26.7618 E, wooded slope of the ravine (*Robinia pseudoacacia* forest with *Anthriscus sylvestris* and *Chelidonium majus*), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀; Lenkivtsi env. 48.5139 N, 26.7929 E, deciduous forest (slope of the ravine), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv (city park), 15.05.2013, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 18.09.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 31.05.2016, 1 ♀; 22.08.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 17.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2921 N, 30.555 E, crossroads in deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 14.05.2021, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4693 N, 30.317 E, crossroads in mixed forest, 14.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2919 E, clearing in mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5021 N, 30.2828 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 31.08.2021, 1 ♂; 08.09.2021, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5042 N, 30.2714 E, road in mixed forest, 08.09.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2022, 1 ♀; 10.05.2022, 1 ♀; 14.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6537 N, 29.4863 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along channel), 02.09.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Stara Rafalivka env. 51.3789 N, 25.8628 E, Styr River bank), 17.08.2020, 1 ♂; Sarny env. 51.3211 N, 26.6727 E, deciduous forest, 19.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytisia env. 48.6945 N, 22.431 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 03.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytisia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytisia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 01.10.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Platycheirus sticticus (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Pocota personata (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrabskyi Park), 02–05.05.2018, 23 ♂; 2 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5042 N, 30.2714 E, road in a mixed forest, 05.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4713 N, 30.2993 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.654 N, 29.4896 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 08.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 14.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 15.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8527 N, 23.0789 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Portevinia maculata (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3059 N, 26.2957 E, deciduous forest with *Allium ursinum*, 20–22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests.

Psarus abdominalis (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5083 N, 30.2639 E, mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♂; 06.07.2018, 1 ♀; 23.07.2020, 1 ♂; 27.07.2020, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5094 N, 30.2618 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 06.07.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2915 E, clearing in mixed forest, 21.05.2020, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4722 N, 30.2905 E, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2021, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2919 E, clearing in mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4728 N, 30.29 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 20.05.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Psilota anthracina Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytisia env. 48.7 N, 22.4313 E, mountain meadow, 06.05.2017, 1 ♂ (G. Popov).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Psilota atra (Fallén, 1817)

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Psilota innupta Rondani, 1857

Material examined. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4713 N, 30.2993 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); 11.05.2019, 1 ♂; 13.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5031 N, 30.2807 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.04.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); 01.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 28.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 13.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.04.2020, 2 ♂; 3 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀; 29.04.2021, 1 ♀; 01.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4709 N, 30.2911 E, edge of mixed forest, 29.04.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6519 N, 29.4888 E, sparse patch of mixed forest, 10.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2020, 1 ♀; 12.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.657 N, 29.5001 E, roadside (near Teteriv River floodplain, 10.05.2021, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; 06.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14–15.05.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 23.04.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 10.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6399 N, 29.4738 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia.

Pyrophaena granditarsa (Forster, 1771)

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6559 N, 29.4941 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 15.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A.

Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Khmil env. 51.4787 N, 27.3098 E, spring fen (Bile Lake bank), 13.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.5952 N, 27.0902 E, meadows among thickets of woody vegetation), 21.08.2020, 3 ♂; 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & A. Martynov); Stare Selo env. 51.6748 N, 27.114 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychy env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, Esman River valley, 25.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Pyrophaena rosarum (Fabricius, 1787)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 01.06.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 02.09.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 25.06.2017, 1 ♂; 23.07.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 5 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & A. Martynov); Illyashivka 50.2793 N, 26.2856 E, meadow slope), 23.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Nazarenko); Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7086 E, swamp), 12.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka); Khmil env. 51.4921 N, 27.2917 E, edge of the swamp (road in mixed forest between Belsk and Khmil), 13.06.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Rudka env. 51.4789 N, 25.6854 E, swamp), 18.08.2020, 1 ♀; Khmil env. 51.4921 N, 27.2917 E, edge of the swamp (road in mixed forest between Belsk and Khmil), 20.08.2020, 1 ♀; Stare Selo env. 51.6748 N, 27.114 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♀; Velyka Lyubasha 50.9549 N, 26.365 E, wet meadow (Zamchisko River valley), 27.05.2021, 1 ♂; Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4126 N, 23.6832 E, Tereblia River bank, meadow near stream), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Rhingia campestris Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4962 N, 26.6508 E, Dnister River bank), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂; Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); 20.05.2021, 1 ♂; 28.04.2016, 3 ♂; 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); 19.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2876 N, 30.5524 E, deciduous forest, 20.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha 50.3009 N, 26.246 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; Illyashivka env. 50.2833 N, 26.29 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♂; Novomalyn 50.2973 N, 26.3718 E, on the garden plot, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 13.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4089 N, 23.6754 E, swamped meadow along stream (Tereblia River valley), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Bilasovytzia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 06.09.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Rhingia rostrata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Banychy env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E), 13.10.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytzia env. 48.6946 N, 22.4302 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), 04.05.2017, 1 ♂ (G. Popov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4169 N, 23.6793 E, beech forest, along stream, 22.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Scaeva dignota (Rondani, 1857)

Material examined. Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E), 01.07.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytzia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Wood-and-Steppe.

Scaeva pyrastris (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0472 N, 31.8957 E, on the garden plot, 19–20.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kherson:** Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe), 09–15.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). **Khmelnyskyi:** Storonyche env. 50.2191 N, 26.584 E, dry meadow, 18.07.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6567 N, 29.4975 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 30.07.2016, 1 ♂; 02.07.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 17.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.636 N, 29.4927 E, clearing in mixed forest, 03.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6323 N, 29.4829 E, felling in mixed forest, 08.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Staiky env. 50.0514 N, 30.9335 E, on the garden plot at the edge of mixed forest, 28.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22–23.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 13.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Volyn:** Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonka Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6475 N, 29.4623 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 31.07.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 02.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Sumy, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Scaeva selenitica (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.0818 N, 31.8899 E, dry meadow, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kodra env. 50.6426 N, 29.511 E, clearing in mixed forest, 30.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5051 N, 30.5465 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 06.04.2016, 1 ♀; Kyiv 50.4989 N, 30.5427 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv 50.4208 N, 30.4933 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), roadside), 29.03.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 13.04.2018, 1 ♀; 31.03.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6576 N, 29.5019 E, edge of mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 01.06.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4951 E,

edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; 01.06.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04–06.06.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2979 N, 26.2638 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2939 N, 26.2883 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ternopil:** Mysyky env. 50.1044 N, 25.4881 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Volyn:** Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 17.07.2022, 1 ♂; 19.07.2022, 1 ♀; 22.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonja Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Selezivka env. 51.54 N, 28.1024 E, road in mixed forest, 15.07.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 12.06.2022, 1 ♂; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2024, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4724 E, on the garden plot, 16.06.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Sericomyia (Arctophila) bombiformis (Fallén, 1810)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Khreshchatyk 48.6314 N, 25.7377 E, meadow slope on the right bank of the Dnister River (near Zalishchyky), 26.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (R. Kryvosheyev). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhvska Mt.), 1300–1600 m a.s.l., 27.07.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Martynov); Stara Huta 48.63 N, 24.21 E, mixed forest (Gorgany Mts.), 22.06.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 29.08.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18–22.07.2022, 6 ♂; 4 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 26–27.08.2023, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Sericomyia (Arctophila) superbiens (Müller, 1776)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Stara Huta 48.63 N, 24.21 E, mixed forest (Gorgany Mts.), 22.06.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.144 N, 24.5494 E, raised bog in *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1415 N, 24.5483 E, raised bog in *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1576 N, 24.5283 E, glades in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Sericomyia (Sericomyia) lappona (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Khreshchatyk 48.6314 N, 25.7377 E, meadow slope on the right bank of the Dnister River (near Zalishchyky), 26.05.2018, 1 ♂ (R. Kryvosheyev). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bilsk env. 51.481 N, 27.2863 E, mixed forest among bogs), 28.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Rivne. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Sericomyia (Sericomyia) silentis (Harris, 1776)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.157 N, 24.529 E, mountain meadow, 05.07.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 10.09.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 05.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6487 N, 29.4888 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 11.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4843 E, grassy vegetation on the bank of the channel), 31.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bilsk env. 51.4907 N, 27.284 E, mixed forest with flowering *Ledum palustre*, 28.05.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kolochava env. 48.4026 N, 23.7783 E, clearing in mountain mixed forest (grassy slope), 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 06.09.2023, 1 ♂; 08.09.2023, 1 ♀; Bilasovytsia env. 48.8498 N, 23.0475 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 11.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window), 05.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Spazigaster ambulans (Fabricius, 1798)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Vorokhta env. 48.1415 N, 24.5483 E, raised bog in *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk); Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀; 13.08.2023, 1 ♂; Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, mountain slope at the edge of *Picea* forest, roadside with flowering *Cirsium palustre*, 11–12.08.2023, 1 ♂; 12 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Sphaerophoria hongjini Bańkowska, 1964

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 04.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Stare Selo env. 51.5952 N, 27.0902 E, meadows among thickets of woody vegetation), 21.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, road along stream, 08.06.2017, 1 ♂; 11.06.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Sphaerophoria interrupta (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Irshava, 25.05.1953, 1 ♂ (V. Ermolenko).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Sphaerophoria philanthus* (Meigen, 1822)**

Material examined. Rivne: Stare Selo env. 51.6721 N, 27.1595 E, channel in mixed forest, 21.08.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Sphaerophoria rueppellii* (Wiedemann, 1830)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5181 N, 26.7915 E, bottom of the ravine, along stream (Sursha River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kherson: Hola Prystan, 12.08.2015, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). Kyiv: Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). Sumy: Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 27.07.2018, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Zhytomyr: Berezova Hat env. 50.4712 N, 28.1203 E, Tnia River valley, bank of the river, 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 21.06.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kherson, Kyiv, Sumy, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

***Sphaerophoria scripta* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kherson: Zelenivka 46.7081 N, 32.6038 E, steppe, 09–15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Nova Buda env. 50.6835 N, 29.7106 E, wet glades in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 14.04.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6329 N, 29.4822 E, felling in mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Odesa: Prymorske env. 45.6756 N, 29.8689 E, steppe area on the Black Sea coast, 07–08.06.2023, 1 ♂ (Ye. Khalaim). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Ternopil: Hutysko env. 49.4039 N, 24.8315 E, meadow slopes, 16.07.2019, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev). Vinnytsia: Stryzhavka env. 49.2894 N, 28.474 E, edge of Southern Bug River floodplain forest, 20.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream, 10.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Zhytomyr: Selezivka env. 51.54 N, 28.1024 E, road in mixed forest, 15.07.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 30.04.2021, 1 ♂; Pokostivka env. 50.2229 N, 28.1803 E, mixed forest, 11.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 25.09.2024, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Ternopil, Vinnytsia, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

***Sphaerophoria taeniata* (Meigen, 1822)**

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4922 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 18.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Mosty 50.3056 N, 26.1912 E, Zbytynka River bank, 23.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15–16.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, Esman River valley, 24–25.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Sphaerophoria virgata* Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1974**

Material examined. Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.473 N, 30.2897 E, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Khmil env. 51.4921 N, 27.2917 E, edge of the swamp (road in mixed forest between Belsk and Khmil), 20.08.2020, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Sphegina (Asiosphegina) sibirica* Stackelberg, 1953**

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6911 N, 22.458 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.7691 N, 22.7418 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 13.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Sphegina (Sphegina) clavata* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Khmelnytskyi: Kavetchina 48.5005 N, 26.6483 E, upper part of wooded ravine, roadside with thickets of flowering *Anthriscus sylvestris* (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2732 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 24.06.2020, 1 ♂; 30.06.2021, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 14.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 12.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2973 N, 26.2786 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 17.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kamianytsia env. 48.6916 N, 22.4571 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6911 N, 22.458 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

***Sphegina (Sphegina) clunipes* (Fallén, 1816)**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Synevyr env. 48.5223 N, 23.6836 E, swampy lake shore in *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

***Sphegina (Sphegina) elegans* Schummel, 1843**

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.5411 N, 27.0294 E, floodplain forest along the Dnister River tributary, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Khmelnytskyi: Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 11.07.2007, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2732 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 24.06.2020, 3 ♂; 7 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Balyko-Shchuchynka env. 49.9624 N, 31.1191 E, ravine in deciduous forest, 05.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 26.06.2021, 5 ♂; 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2721 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 30.06.2021, 2 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 31.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4855 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Lypovets env. 48.7726 N, 22.74 E, meadows at the edge of deciduous forest, 21.07.2024, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6911 N, 22.458 E, deciduous forest, 10–11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Sphegina (Sphegina) latifrons* Egger, 1865**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; 12.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1421 N, 24.5479 E, mountain slope

at the edge of *Picea* forest, roadside with flowering *Cirsium palustre*, 11–12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8404 N, 23.1181 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 17.05.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Sphiximorpha garibaldii Rondani, 1860

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5025 N, 30.2829 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Sphiximorpha subsessilis (Illiger in Rossi, 1807)

Material examined. Kherson: Kherson 46.6685 N, 32.644 E, 04.05.2020, 4 ♂; 2 ♀ (R. Mishustin). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.5147 N, 30.5446 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♂; Kyiv 50.4989 N, 30.5427 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♂; Kyiv 50.5041 N, 30.542 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♂; Kyiv 50.5147 N, 30.5446 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 26.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5083 N, 30.2635 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5218 N, 30.5505 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 28.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha 50.3021 N, 26.3043 E, edge of old overgrown felling in deciduous forest, 17.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Steppe.

Spilomyia diophthalma (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hutyshche env. 51.7381 N, 32.6238 E, dry meadow, 06.08.2022, 1 ♀; Khlopianky env. 51.7276 N, 32.7296 E, dry meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 12.08.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Khmelnyskyi:** Storonyche env. 50.2191 N, 26.584 E, dry meadow, 18.07.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 07.08.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5043 N, 30.274 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.07.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.08.2020, 1 ♂; 09.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6581 N, 29.4994 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4944 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2779 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6842 N, 29.7084 E, swampy glades in mixed forest, 07.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 21.08.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.07.2022, 1 ♂; 06.08.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6316 N, 29.4851 E, road in mixed forest along the felling, 10.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 17.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4861 E, Teteriv River floodplain (edge of a dry meadow on the sandy hill), 19.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 23.07.2023, 1 ♀; 25.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6541 N, 29.487 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4871 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, among thickets of shrubs, 05.08.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 11.08.2024, 1 ♂; 24.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov). **Zhytomyr:** Kamyanka env. 51.175 N, 27.5342 E, Ubort River bank, 17.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Spilomyia manicata (Rondani, 1865)

Material examined. Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.32 N, 30.53 E, 12.08.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5043 N, 30.274 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.07.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6566 N, 29.4968 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 09.08.2020, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2779 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.4963 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 31.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2227 N, 30.5196 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 03.08.2021, 1 ♀; Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.219 N, 30.5207 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 03.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 24.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.08.2024, 1 ♂; 11.08.2024, 1 ♂; 24.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Kochergy env. 51.48 N, 33.8677 E, edge of deciduous forest, 28.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonja Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Spilomyia saltuum (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.07.2020, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2779 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂; 27.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5224 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 25.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6337 N, 29.4804 E, felling in mixed forest, 25.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 31.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Syrirta pipiens (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8956 E, on the garden plot, 04.08.2018, 1 ♀; Nizhyn 51.0091 N, 31.8611 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Bernove env. 48.486 N, 26.6508 E, edge of deciduous planting (Dnister River valley), 22.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kherson:** Antonivka env. 46.674 N, 32.7702 E, 15.05.2020, 1 ♂ (R. Mishustin). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 28.04.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 04.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Khodosivka 50.2694 N, 30.5011 E, Vita River valley, 17.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.657 N, 29.4988 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (along channel), 25.08.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2177 N, 30.5226 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 23.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 08.04.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4724 N, 30.2891 E, old overgrown felling in mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6468 N, 29.5164 E, road in mixed forest, 14.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E,

edge of mixed forest along railway, 03–05.06.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Maiaky env. 46.4123 N, 30.165 E, Dniester River floodplain, 24.09.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Rivne:** Buderazh env. 50.3189 N, 26.15 E, meadow slopes, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Ternopil:** Zhnyborody env. 48.9028 N, 25.4251 E, 19.07.2019, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev); Scala Podilska 48.8373 N, 26.2185 E, Zbruch River valley, 26.07.2019, 1 ♂ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 01.06.2015, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 02.10.2023, 1 ♀; 25.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Ternopil, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Syrphus ribesii (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Mylnyky env. 51.0314 N, 31.7752 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.325 N, 30.5292 E, edge of deciduous forest, 12.06.2015, 1 ♀; Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 23.07.2015, 1 ♂; 28.04.2016, 1 ♀; 10.04.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Zavorychi env. 50.6794 N, 31.0937 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 1 ♂; 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 30.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.503 N, 30.28 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 25.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6476 N, 29.4868 E, road in mixed forest, 17.04.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.04.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 15.10.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 14.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3003 N, 26.2554 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2020, 1 ♂; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytisia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂; Kamianytisia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4009 N, 23.7816 E, glade in mixed forest, near stream, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 07.09.2023, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7989 N, 22.8001 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 18.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Syrphus torvus Osten Sacken, 1875

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0472 N, 31.8957 E, on the garden plot, 19–20.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1622 N, 24.5361 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Zarusliak and Pozhyzhevskva Mt.), 09.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1573 N, 24.5286 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 12.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Khmelnytskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dniester River val-

ley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.07.2015, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.04.2016, 2 ♂; 1 ♀; Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 10.09.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6476 N, 29.4868 E, road in mixed forest, 17.04.2017, 1 ♀; Kyiv 50.5058 N, 30.5443 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 17.04.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 28.04.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6557 N, 29.4998 E, mixed forest, 09.04.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4939 E, mixed forest, 17.04.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4968 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 17.04.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.10.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 10–13.04.2018, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4946 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17–24.04.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2992 N, 26.2406 E, Zbytnka River floodplain forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.4863 N, 25.7095 E, swamp, 18.08.2020, 1 ♀; Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Berezhnitsia env. 51.4439 N, 26.4985 E, edge of mixed forest over the Horyn River valley, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 13.05.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytisia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Kolochava env. 48.4613 N, 23.7012 E, meadow slope (Pishkonja Ridge), 19.07.2022, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8519 N, 23.0756 E, mixed forest, 29.04.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, edge of mixed forest, 03.05.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6405 N, 29.472 E, on the garden plot, 15.10.2021, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 15.04.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 23.04.2022, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6406 N, 29.4721 E, inside the veranda on the window, 28.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Syrphus vitripennis Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Chernihiv: Mylnyky env. 51.0314 N, 31.7752 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 22.07.2015, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Piskivka env. 50.6902 N, 29.6913 E, clearing in mixed forest, 23.04.2016, 1 ♀; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5088 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 19.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6573 N, 29.4995 E, Teteriv River floodplain, roadside (near mixed forest, 04.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*), 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; 18.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Balyko-Shchuchynka env. 49.9624 N, 31.1191 E, ravine in deciduous forest, 05.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6543 N, 29.4911 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Odesa:** Maryanivka env. 46.3995 N, 30.4996 E, forest shelter belt, 24.04.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Prymorske env. 45.6756 N, 29.8689 E, steppe area on the Black Sea coast, 07–08.06.2023, 1 ♀ (Ye. Khalaim). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow, 17.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Vinnitsia:** Stryzhavka env. 49.2894 N, 28.474 E, edge of Southern Bug River floodplain forest, 20.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Volyn:** Zubylne env. 50.8196 N, 24.7969 E, edge of deciduous forest, 28.04.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka);

Sirnychky env. 50.7848 N, 24.9285 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2020, 1 ♂; Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 07.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6988 N, 22.4449 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♀; 09.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8542 N, 23.072 E, mountain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 23.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Selezivka env. 51.54 N, 28.1024 E, road in mixed forest, 15.07.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Bila Krynytsia 50.6403 N, 29.4722 E, on the garden plot, 09.05.2020, 1 ♂; Ukrainka env. 50.7607 N, 29.4129 E, Irsha River floodplain meadow, 17.08.2020, 1 ♀; Bila Krynytsia 50.6407 N, 29.4718 E, on the garden plot, 29.04.2024, 1 ♂; Zelena Poliana env. 50.6001 N, 28.1255 E, mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Odesa, Rivne, Vinnytsia, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Syrphus vitripennis Meigen, 1823

Material examined. Zakarpatska: Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Temnostoma apiforme (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3018 N, 26.3016 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3023 N, 26.301 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♀; Illyashivka env. 50.2825 N, 26.2822 E, mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20–22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians.

Temnostoma bombylans (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0084 N, 31.857 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2022, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskyi Park), 05.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Chernivtsi:** Lenkivtsi env. 48.514 N, 26.7955 E, deciduous forest, along stream (Sursha River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Khmelnyskyi:** Kavetchina 48.4975 N, 26.6511 E, road in a wooded ravine along stream (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.4224 N, 30.4946 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), 30.05.2007, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 06.06.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 04.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6574 N, 29.4963 E, Teteriv River floodplain meadow, 26.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♀; 01.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 04.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Sobolivka env. 50.7291 N, 30.8156 E, mixed forest near pond (Zalissia National Nature Park), 22.06.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.05.2024, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka 50.2789 N, 26.2819 E, edge of deciduous forest (with overmature trees of *Tilia* sp.), 11.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3018 N, 26.3016 E, old over-

grown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2976 N, 26.2635 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.6943 N, 22.4303 E, Uzh River valley (left bank), edge of deciduous forest, 09.05.2017, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 10.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Polianska Huta env. 48.7481 N, 22.7714 E, deciduous forest, 18.05.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Temnostoma meridionale Krivosheina & Mamayev, 1962

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.514 N, 26.7955 E, deciduous forest, along stream (Sursha River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, near stream, 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Lisnyky env. 50.2956 N, 30.5497 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6565 N, 29.4966 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 27.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.05.2021, 1 ♀; 29.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4902 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 08.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 14.05.2023, 1 ♂; 17.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 03.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2828 N, 26.2784 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; 22.05.2019, 1 ♀; Illyashivka env. 50.277 N, 26.278 E, deciduous forest, 21.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2992 N, 26.2406 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 10–11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Temnostoma vespiforme (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn env. 51.0442 N, 31.8031 E, deciduous forest (Vetkhe tract), 06.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.06.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♂; 04.06.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6513 N, 29.4885 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 28.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka 50.2789 N, 26.2819 E, edge of deciduous forest (with overmature trees of *Tilia* sp.), 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; Il-

Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Mereshor env. 48.4078 N, 23.6899 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4164 N, 23.6808 E, beech forest, along stream, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (N. Nazarov); Synevyr env. 48.5313 N, 23.65 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7785 N, 22.7665 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Ivanivka env. 50.7019 N, 28.3641 E, felling in mixed forest, 10.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Trichopsomyia flavitarsis (Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Kyiv: Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 21.06.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

Trichopsomyia joratensis Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1997

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.158 N, 24.5354 E, 27.06.2008, 1 ♂ (V. Shparyk).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk. **Zones:** Carpathians.

Triglyphus primus Loew, 1840

Material examined. Chernihiv: Yabluneve env. 51.1057 N, 31.8728 E, forest shelter belt, 13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Dibrova env. 50.1944 N, 30.2036 E, 01.07.2006, 1 ♀; 24.07.2007, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 06.07.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.6837 N, 29.7036 E, overgrown damp road in mixed forest, 16.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11–13.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bereznytsia env. 51.4292 N, 26.4892 E, glades among thickets of woody vegetation (Horyn River valley), 19.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 06.08.2018, 1 ♂; 10.08.2018, 1 ♂; 13.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Banychi env. 51.51 N, 33.93 E, 16.08.2018, 1 ♂; 21.08.2018, 1 ♂; 04.09.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy. **Zones:** Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Tropidia scita (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Hvylivka env. 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Chernivtsi: Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25–26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kherson: Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E, 14.05.2020, 1 ♂; 25.05.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). Khmelnitskyi: Storonyche env. 50.2191 N, 26.584 E, dry meadow, 18.07.2018, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5096 N, 30.263 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 27.05.2015, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 3 ♂; 2 ♀; 02.06.2016, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 20.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 06.07.2018, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2833 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 19.06.2020, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2873 N, 30.556 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 09.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2969 N, 26.2389 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 13.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zhy-**

tomyr: Berezova Hat env. 50.4707 N, 28.1185 E, wet meadows among shrubs (Tnia River valley), 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Khmelnitskyi, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Volucella bombylans (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5393 N, 26.76 E, deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.538 N, 27.0298 E, wet meadow along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 25.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Komariv env. 48.5272 N, 27.033 E, thickets of *Anthriscus sylvestris* along the Dnister River tributary at the edge of deciduous forest, 26.05.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1400–1500 m a.s.l., 29.07.2008, 1 ♂ (K. Martynova); Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6505 N, 29.5093 E, mixed forest, 30.05.2015, 1 ♀; Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.05.2016, 3 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & M. Zaika); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2823 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; 06.06.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 20.05.2023, 1 ♂; 25.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 26–27.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Ilyashivka 50.2815 N, 26.2881 E, areas of meadow vegetation among shrubs, along channels, 10.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2962 N, 26.239 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♀; Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3018 N, 26.3016 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Ilyashivka env. 50.2825 N, 26.2822 E, road in mixed forest, 19.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bilsk env. 51.4907 N, 27.284 E, mixed forest with flowering *Ledum palustre*, 28.05.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytnka River floodplain meadow, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2965 N, 26.2416 E, mixed forest among lowland calcareous fens, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11–13.05.2018, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyana-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Volucella inanis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1541 N, 24.5308 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (between Pozhyzhevska Mt. and Zarosliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Khmelnitskyi: Dubivka env. 49.1327 N, 26.4427 E, edge of mixed forest, 06.08.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 29.07.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5043 N, 30.274 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Rzhyshechiv 49.9664 N, 31.1046 E, steppe ravine, 06.08.2020, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2237 N, 30.5193 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 25.07.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 11.08.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6551 N, 29.4908 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 17.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1

♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Lviv:** Piatnychany env. 49.3584 N, 23.9241 E, edge of deciduous forest, roadside, 17.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Ternopil:** Hutyisko env. 49.4039 N, 24.8315 E, meadow slopes, 16.07.2019, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Zakarpatska:** Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8273 N, 23.1051 E, edge of mixed forest, 19.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 26.08.2023, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Lviv, Ternopil, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Volucella inflata (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 06.06.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Irpin env. 50.5038 N, 30.2767 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 19.06.2020, 1 ♂; 3 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2721 E, road in mixed forest along railway, 30.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6318 N, 29.4803 E, old felling in mixed forest, 02.07.2021, 1 ♀; Kodra env. 50.629 N, 29.4803 E, mixed forest with predominance of *Quercus robur*, 03.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 29.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 10.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀; Kodra env. 50.6287 N, 29.4797 E, road in mixed forest, 26.06.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 20.05.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6546 N, 29.4892 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 26.05.2023, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 01.06.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3083 N, 26.2886 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 12.06.2021, 3 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Volucella pellucens pellucens (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0091 N, 31.8611 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Chernivtsi:** Spaska env. 48.3017 N, 25.7759 E, meadow, 430 m a.s.l., 24.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka). **Kyiv:** Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.06.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2016, 1 ♂; Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 29.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 02.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5083 N, 30.2639 E, mixed forest along railway, 01.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Fenevychi env. 50.8721 N, 30.01 E, edge of mixed forest, 30.05.2019, 1 ♂ (I. Pljushtch); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.06.2020, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 27.07.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀; 22.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Ternopil:** Beremyany env. 48.8694 N, 25.4196 E, Strypa River mouth, 20.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S. & V. Korneyev).

Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4136 N, 23.6824 E, Tereblia River bank, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrurka); Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Ternopil, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Volucella zonaria (Poda, 1761)

Material examined. Kharkiv: Gaidary env. 49.6232 N, 36.3285 E, Siverskyi Donets River floodplain meadow, 16.08.2009, 1 ♀ (K. Martynova). **Kyiv:** Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2186 N, 30.5205 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine), 03.09.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.06.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4898 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6542 N, 29.4868 E, aspen grove in floodplain meadow (near channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 24.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.4224 N, 30.4946 E, wooded ravine in the city (Protasiv Yar), 08–14.08.2007, 1 ♂; 4 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 10.06.2018, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.701 N, 22.4371 E, deciduous forest, 07–08.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kharkiv, Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Xanthandrus comtus (Harris, 1780)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafyskyi Park), 01.06.2018, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0471 N, 31.8956 E, on the garden plot, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂; Hvylyivka env. 50.9724 N, 31.8721 E, dry meadow, 14.06.2018, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1634 N, 24.5429 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (Zarosliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♂; Vorokhta env. 48.1602 N, 24.5217 E, raised bog at the edge of *Picea* mountain forest, 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.5028 N, 30.2848 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2918 N, 30.554 E, deciduous forest, 10.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Koblytsia env. 50.783 N, 29.919 E, deciduous forest, 16.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5026 N, 30.2835 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 06.07.2018, 1 ♂; 23.07.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 02.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2195 N, 30.5224 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (upper part of meadow slopes), 25.07.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6545 N, 29.4929 E, swampy glades at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 09.11.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6526 N, 29.4836 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Ilyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 17.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kvasy env. 48.1502 N, 24.5105 E, meadow (Breskul Mt.), 1700–1800 m a.s.l., 31.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kolochava env. 48.4756 N, 23.7164 E, glade in *Picea* mountain forest (Pishkonja Ridge),

19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Kolochava env. 48.405 N, 23.7927 E, road in mixed forest (over the Prisplog pass), 20.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 21.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Pashkivtsi env. 48.8102 N, 22.8614 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21–22.07.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23–24.07.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4723 E, on the garden plot, 30.03.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Xanthogramma citrofasciatum (De Geer, 1776)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0486 N, 31.8714 E, pond shore, 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). Chernivtsi: Lenkivtsi env. 48.5318 N, 26.7642 E, bottom of the ravine (Sara-Lunga River valley), 23.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Khmelnytskyi: Kavetchina 48.4971 N, 26.6508 E, grassy slopes (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5089 N, 30.2631 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 11.05.2011, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Lisnyky env. 50.2961 N, 30.536 E, deciduous forest, 03.05.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.701 N, 22.4368 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bilasovytzia env. 48.8507 N, 23.0435 E, edge of mixed forest, 09.05.2023, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Kamianytsia env. 48.6999 N, 22.4319 E, mountain meadow, 06–07.05.2017, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zhytomyr: Bronyky env. 50.5611 N, 27.7907 E, Tnia River bank, 26.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Khmelnytskyi, Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Xanthogramma dives (Rondani, 1857)

Material examined. Cherkasy: Buchak Lake env. 49.8568 N, 31.4371 E, edge of deciduous forest, 10.07.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrasky Park), 10.05.2018, 1 ♂; Morivsk 51.0884 N, 30.8826 E, on the garden plot, 14.07.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Morivsk env. 51.11 N, 30.8869 E, oak planting along the cliff above the oxbow of the Desna River, 09.07.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Hutyshe env. 51.7381 N, 32.6238 E, dry meadow, 06.08.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka); Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0541 N, 31.9063 E, Oster River bank, 03.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). Chernivtsi: Bernove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♂; Bernove 48.4907 N, 26.6461 E, roadside (Dnister River valley), 22.05.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Lenkivtsi env. 48.538 N, 26.7592 E, upper edge of deciduous forest (Sara-Lunga River valley), 24.05.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Kherson: Kherson 46.6541 N, 32.5575 E, 25.05.2020, 1 ♀ (R. Mishustin). Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 05.06.2015, 1 ♀; Zavorychi env. 50.6809 N, 31.0894 E, meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Nova Buda env. 50.688 N, 29.736 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2016, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 21.05.2016, 6 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5214 N, 30.2746 E, edge of mixed forest near Irpin River floodplain, 23.08.2016, 1 ♂; Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2802 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 17.05.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 20.05.2017, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2802 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 25.06.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2918 N, 30.554 E, deciduous forest, 17.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.5004 E, road in mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain, 27.05.2018, 1 ♀; Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2802 E, edge of mixed forest along railway,

26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.296 N, 30.5347 E, edge of deciduous forest, 03.05.2019, 1 ♂; Kotsiubynske env. 50.4728 N, 30.3209 E, clearing in mixed forest, 11.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 08.05.2020, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18.05.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 23.05.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kotsiubynske env. 50.4708 N, 30.2919 E, clearing in mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5015 N, 30.2833 E, wet glades in the Lyubka River floodplain forest, 16.09.2021, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 03.05.2024, 1 ♂; 08.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Illyashivka env. 50.2777 N, 26.2808 E, edge of deciduous forest, 21.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Rudka env. 51.5251 N, 25.7008 E, waterlogged meadow near mixed forest, 18.08.2020, 1 ♂; Bilsk env. 51.4907 N, 27.284 E, mixed forest with flowering *Ledum palustre*, 28.05.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20–22.05.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.698 N, 22.4463 E, deciduous forest, 11.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Polianska Huta env. 48.7481 N, 22.7714 E, deciduous forest, 18.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). Zhytomyr: Zelena Poliana env. 50.6001 N, 28.1255 E, mixed forest, 08.05.2024, 1 ♂; Ocheretianka env. 50.5017 N, 28.1232 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka); Ivanivka env. 50.7019 N, 28.3641 E, felling in mixed forest, 10.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka).

Distribution. Regions: Cherkasy, Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe, Steppe.

Xanthogramma laetum (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2389 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2992 N, 26.2406 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Mosty env. 50.275 N, 26.1997 E, deciduous forest, 23.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2942 N, 26.2395 E, lowland calcareous fen in mixed forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2973 N, 26.2786 E, edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 17.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2018, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 08–10.06.2018, 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.6983 N, 22.4306 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.05.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia.

Xanthogramma pedissequum (Harris, 1778)

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhynske env. 50.9881 N, 31.8011 E, wet meadow at the edge of deciduous forest, 19.06.2022, 1 ♀ (V. Kavrka). Ivano-Frankivsk: Mykhalche env. 48.7826 N, 25.5756 E, Dnister River bank, edge of deciduous forest, 15.06.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavrka). Kyiv: Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 06.06.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2209 N, 30.518 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 05.07.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 26.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 25.08.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.5218 N, 30.5505 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River), 28.05.2019, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6564 N, 29.4962 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 09.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.504 N, 30.2781 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4922 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 24.06.2022, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.484 E, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6532 N, 29.4849 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 05.07.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env.

50.6528 N, 29.4838 E, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 31.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Berezhnitsia env. 51.4293 N, 26.4867 E, Horyn River valley, roadside, 19.08.2020, 1 ♀; Berezhnitsia env. 51.4439 N, 26.4985 E, edge of mixed forest over the Horyn River valley, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Sarny env. 51.3146 N, 26.674 E, edge of deciduous forest, 30.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Sumy:** Matskove env. 51.49 N, 33.91 E, Esman River valley, 15.07.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianitsia env. 48.7005 N, 22.434 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8516 N, 23.0627 E, mountain meadow, 850 m a.s.l., 19.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka 48.8447 N, 23.0993 E, 20.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.08.2023, 1 ♂; Bilasovetsia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 3 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 26.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.855 N, 23.0862 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 02.09.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 06.09.2023, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianitsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 10–11.06.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia 50.6404 N, 29.4721 E, on the garden plot, 12.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Xanthogramma stackelbergi Violovitsh, 1975

Material examined. Kyiv: Irpin env. 50.5088 N, 30.2631 E, mixed forest along railway, 23.08.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Olshanytsia env. 49.6 N, 30.6 E, felling in mixed forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Nova Buda env. 50.6839 N, 29.7104 E, glades in mixed forest, 07.08.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kodra env. 50.6306 N, 29.4871 E, road in mixed forest, 14.07.2023, 1 ♀; 23.07.2023, 1 ♀; 25.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kolochava env. 48.414 N, 23.7972 E, old beech forest, 20.07.2022, 1 ♀ (K. Gushtan); Lypovets env. 48.7701 N, 22.7443 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 18.07.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Kamianitsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 09–10.06.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Xylota abiens Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0084 N, 31.857 E, deciduous forest, 09.06.2022, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0091 N, 31.8611 E, mixed forest, 01.06.2023, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0093 N, 31.8574 E, mixed forest, 02.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). **Kyiv:** Kyiv 50.5146 N, 30.5445 E, Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River, city park), 18.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2016, 1 ♂; 20.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5045 N, 30.2835 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 04.06.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mali Dmytrovychi env. 50.2209 N, 30.518 E, wooded ravine among agricultural fields, 05.07.2017, 1 ♂; 13.07.2017, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Leonivka env. 50.794 N, 29.9098 E, felling in mixed forest, 16.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2020, 1 ♂; 01.06.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 01.06.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; 17.05.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Bushcha env. 50.2941 N, 26.2877 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 11.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2998 N, 26.2416 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2981 N, 26.2629 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.05.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3066 N, 26.2943 E, deciduous forest (My-

zotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2976 N, 26.2635 E, meadow at the edge of Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 13.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

Xylota caeruleiventris Zetterstedt, 1838

Material examined. Kyiv: Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 21.05.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Kholm env. 51.4781 N, 27.3081 E, mixed forest among spring fens (Bile Lake bank), 20.08.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 9 ♂; 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Rivne. **Zones:** Polissia.

Xylota florum (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Kyiv: Leonivka env. 50.787 N, 29.9195 E, felling in mixed forest, 16.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 04.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6563 N, 29.4964 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 19.05.2024, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 29.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6527 N, 29.4902 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and mixed forest, 05.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Kamianitsia env. 48.6911 N, 22.458 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4078 N, 23.6899 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4147 N, 23.6644 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 19.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7691 N, 22.7418 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 13.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Zhytomyr:** Bila Krynytsia env. 50.6553 N, 29.477 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the river), 31.05.2015, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Xylota jakutorum Bagatshanova, 1980

Material examined. Chernihiv: Vertiivka env. 51.1763 N, 31.8185 E, edge of deciduous forest (Boromyky), 22.05.2019, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). **Ivano-Frankivsk:** Vorokhta env. 48.1576 N, 24.5283 E, glades in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog, 13.08.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Kyiv:** Potashnia env. 50.7143 N, 29.7371 E, Tal River floodplain forest, 24.05.2016, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6544 N, 29.4908 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 25.05.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.09.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). **Rivne:** Bilsk env. 51.481 N, 27.2863 E, mixed forest among bogs, 28.05.2021, 1 ♀; Hrabun env. 51.546 N, 27.2002 E, glades in mixed forest (with flowering *Ledum palustre* near raised bog), 29.05.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). **Zakarpatska:** Synevyr env. 48.5249 N, 23.6657 E, road in mountain *Picea* forest, 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians, Polissia.

Xylota meigeniana Stackelberg, 1964

Material examined. Kyiv: Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 01.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6537 N, 29.4863 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Distribution. Regions: Kyiv. **Zones:** Polissia.

***Xylota segnis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0472 N, 31.8957 E, on the garden plot, 24.05.2023, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 50.9917 N, 31.885 E, mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂; Nizhyn 51.0544 N, 31.878 E, city park (Hrafskiyi Park), 05.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Chernivtsi: Bemove 48.4908 N, 26.6449 E, lawns among thickets of trees and shrubs (Dnister River valley), 21.05.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Kyiv: Kotsiubynske env. 50.4719 N, 30.3076 E, clearing in mixed forest, 13.05.2016, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov & M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Kyiv 50.3448 N, 30.4853 E, city park (Theophania Park), 31.05.2016, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 10.05.2020, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6554 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 01.06.2020, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 07.09.2023, 1 ♂; 06.09.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♂; 19.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 12.05.2018, 1 ♂; 13.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2968 N, 26.2394 E, mixed forest at the edge of lowland calcareous fen, 12.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.3019 N, 26.3015 E, old overgrown felling in deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 17.05.2018, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.302 N, 26.301 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Sarny env. 51.3211 N, 26.6727 E, deciduous forest, 19.08.2020, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Volyn: Vilka-Sadivska env. 50.746 N, 24.8508 E, deciduous forest, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6947 N, 22.4324 E, felling in deciduous forest, 05.05.2017, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Kamianytsia env. 48.7006 N, 22.4364 E, edge of deciduous forest, 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; Kamianytsia env. 48.7007 N, 22.4384 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 10.06.2018, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀; 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8543 N, 23.0727 E, edge of mixed forest, 20.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.06.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.07.2023, 1 ♀; 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; 19.08.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 25.08.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8541 N, 23.0719 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 28.08.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8291 N, 23.1004 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 07.09.2023, 2 ♂; 2 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Zhytomyr: Natalia env. 50.3747 N, 28.0445 E, mixed forest, 09.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Chernivtsi, Kyiv, Rivne, Volyn, Zakarpatska, Zhytomyr. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Xylota sylvarum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Lisnyky env. 50.288 N, 30.5567 E, meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake), 10.08.2017, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Irpin env. 50.5041 N, 30.2811 E, edge of mixed forest along railway, 20.06.2020, 1 ♂; 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 31.07.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 12.06.2022, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6539 N, 29.4903 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 17.07.2023, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6549 N, 29.4952 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20.05.2019, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 12.06.2021, 1 ♀; Bushcha env. 50.2992 N, 26.2406 E, Zbytynka River floodplain forest, 15.06.2021, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.2953 N, 26.2862 E, Zbytynka River floodplain meadow, 16.06.2021, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6933 N, 22.4543 E, deciduous forest, 11.06.2018, 1 ♀

(A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀; Mereshor env. 48.4156 N, 23.6813 E, beech forest, along stream, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Synyevyr env. 48.5223 N, 23.6827 E, mountain *Picea* forest, near swampy lake), 21.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8536 N, 23.075 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 21.06.2023, 1 ♂; Latorka env. 48.8264 N, 23.112 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 23.07.2023, 1 ♂; 1 ♀; Bilasovytisia env. 48.8443 N, 23.0501 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 22.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Lypovets env. 48.768 N, 22.74 E, road in deciduous forest, along stream, 20.05.2024, 1 ♀; Lypovets env. 48.7778 N, 22.76 E, meadows near stream), 10.06.2024, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 23–24.07.2023, 1 ♂; 3 ♀ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Xylota tarda* Meigen, 1822**

Material examined. Chernihiv: Nizhyn 51.0105 N, 31.8607 E, mixed forest, 28.05.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka). Kyiv: Zavorychi env. 50.6889 N, 31.0824 E, deciduous forest, 16.07.2015, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6562 N, 29.496 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 22.05.2016, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Lisnyky env. 50.2923 N, 30.5547 E, deciduous forest (dry stream bed), 07.08.2019, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6525 N, 29.488 E, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 26.06.2021, 1 ♂; Myhalky env. 50.6548 N, 29.49 E, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 13.09.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Myhalky env. 50.6517 N, 29.4887 E, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 18.06.2024, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. 50.6533 N, 29.4849 E, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 06.09.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Rivne: Illyashivka env. 50.2823 N, 26.2818 E, edge of mixed forest, 16.05.2018, 1 ♂; Bushcha env. 50.3054 N, 26.2968 E, deciduous forest (Myzotskyi Kriazh), 20–22.05.2019, 1 ♂; 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov). Sumy: Banychi env. 51.5 N, 33.92 E, 05.08.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika). Zakarpatska: Mereshor env. 48.4141 N, 23.6809 E, edge of a beech forest (with *Picea abies*) over a meadow slope, 18.07.2022, 2 ♂; 1 ♀ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4156 N, 23.6813 E, beech forest, along stream, 18.07.2022, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4078 N, 23.6899 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 22.07.2022, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4156 N, 23.6813 E, beech forest, along stream, 23.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♀; Latorka env. 48.8252 N, 23.1126 E, meadow at the edge of mixed forest, 20.08.2023, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Chernihiv, Kyiv, Rivne, Sumy, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Broad-Leaved Forests, Carpathians, Polissia, Wood-and-Steppe.

***Xylota xanthocnema* Collin, 1939**

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk: Vorokhta env. 48.1543 N, 24.5353 E, mountain meadow (Pozhyzhevska Mt.), 1300–1500 m a.s.l., 28.07.2016, 1 ♂ (A. Martynov); Vorokhta env. 48.1634 N, 24.5429 E, *Picea* mountain forest, roadside (Zarosliak), 10.08.2023, 1 ♀; Vorokhta env. 48.1576 N, 24.5283 E, glades in *Picea* mountain forest near raised bog), 13.08.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov). Zakarpatska: Kamianytsia env. 48.6937 N, 22.4535 E, deciduous forest, 08.06.2018, 1 ♀; 11.06.2018, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Mereshor env. 48.4051 N, 23.6981 E, road in mixed forest, along stream (Kvasovets), 18.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov & V. Kavurka); Mereshor env. 48.4169 N, 23.6793 E, beech forest, along stream, 23.07.2022, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov); Latorka env. 48.8378 N, 23.121 E, road in mixed forest, along stream, 24.07.2023, 1 ♂; Lypovets env. 48.7909 N, 22.7828 E, mountain meadow (Polonyna-Runa), 1200–1300 m a.s.l., 14.06.2024, 1 ♂ (V. Kavurka).

Distribution. Regions: Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpatska. **Zones:** Carpathians.

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